

INFLUENCE OF PRINCIPALS' ADMINISTRATIVE ROLES ON TEACHERS' PRODUCTIVITY

IN KARU LGA, NASARAWA STATE

BY

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**A DISSERTATION SUBMITTED IN PARTIAL FULFILLMENT OF THE
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DECLARATION

I **Justina Henry Odion**, hereby declare that the project work entitled **Influence of Principals' Administrative Roles on Teachers' Productivity** is a record of an original work done by me as a result of my research effort carried out in the Faculty of Education, National Open University of Nigeria under the supervision of **Dr. M. C Mbanefo**.

CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that this study was carried out by Justina Henry Odion (NOU232154897)
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DEDICATION

I dedicate this work, with a lot of respect and appreciation to my beloved husband Pastor Henry Odion who always stands by me through thin and thick and always tells me that I can make it. And to my late father, Mr. Gandu Raman.

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the influence of principals' administrative roles on teachers' productivity in secondary schools within the Karu Local Government Area of Nasarawa State, focusing on five selected schools. The objectives were to examine the specific administrative roles of principals that influence teachers' productivity, assess the impact of principals' communication roles, evaluate the sustainability of instructional materials, and analyze the effects of a supportive work environment on productivity. Employing a survey research design, the target population comprised all teachers in secondary schools within Karu Local Government Area. From this, a sample of 150 teachers was drawn from two public and three private secondary schools. A self-administered instrument titled "*Questionnaire on the Impact of Principals' Administrative Roles on Teachers' Productivity (QIPARTP)*" was developed, validated, and tested for reliability, achieving a Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of 0.75, indicating acceptable reliability. Data collection involved distributing questionnaires to the sample, with 145 valid responses obtained. Data analysis utilized SPSS software to compute means, standard deviations, and frequency distributions, while a t-test for independent samples tested the hypotheses. The findings revealed that principals' communication roles significantly enhance teachers' productivity and that maintaining instructional materials is crucial for effective teaching outcomes. Additionally, a favorable work environment was strongly associated with increased commitment and productivity among teachers. The study concludes that school leadership focused on effective communication, resource sustainability, and a supportive atmosphere can substantially improve teacher effectiveness.

Key words: Principals' Administrative Roles, Teachers' Productivity, Communication Roles, Instructional Materials Sustainability, and Work Environment

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

The rapid technological advancement in every sphere of human endeavor is highlighted by a knowledge explosion and revolution. The process of applying knowledge, skills, and emerging technologies to improve and preserve the capabilities of members of an organization to execute essential tasks is known as Human Performance Optimization (HPO) (Mbanefo, 2023a). In the current scenario, the roles and functions of teachers as agents of change have become increasingly critical. Teachers are the backbone of schools, and their productivity is vital to the overall effectiveness of the institution. When teachers are dedicated to their work, their professionalism is reflected in their productivity, evidenced by their attendance, enthusiasm, and work ethics.

Regrettably, this has not always been the case; many teachers in our schools today are not committed to their assigned roles. Some are frequently late to school, display a lackadaisical attitude, while others do not even write their lesson notes. Teachers' professionalism is closely associated with high performance, which can be seen in their attendance, enthusiasm for teaching, work motivation, monitoring of students' work, class control, leadership, supervision, and disciplinary abilities (Adeyemi, 2010). Teachers' productivity refers to the results or output that a school system is expected to achieve towards the realization of educational goals and objectives.

In Nigeria's secondary school system, the principal is the highest-ranking administrator. He is the leader, and as such, he is charged with the authority and responsibility of running the school. His leadership role encompasses administrative duties, which involve combining and coordinating the human and material resources in the school through planning, organizing, leading, and monitoring to achieve the goals and objectives of the institution. According to Deal and Peterson (2009), principals

are tasked with designing the school's vision and mission and translating these plans into realistic teaching-learning experiences and co-curricular activities to achieve the school's vision and mission.

Additionally, the administrative role of the principal extends beyond the school to all stakeholders in the education sector, including the host community, school board, government, and parents.

There are expectations from each of these stakeholders regarding the principal's performance. Thus, the administrative role of the principal is a complex one. According to Alberta Education (2009), the principal's administrative responsibilities begin with constructing the school's vision and mission, setting the budget, securing human and material resources, designing school development plans, establishing school rules and regulations, creating and maintaining good relationships with the host community, parents, and staff, gathering useful information, supervising staff activities, conducting whole-school evaluations, and maintaining good relationships with Ministry of Education officials, among other responsibilities.

The Human Rights Declaration of the United Nations (UN) (1948) and the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs), which were to have been achieved by 2015, both require increased participation in education as well as improvements in the quality of education, which in turn demand effective performance from the school principal. The quality of the principal's administrative performance can significantly affect the quality of education provided in the school and the instructional productivity of the teachers. For the principal to fulfill these roles effectively and meet stakeholder expectations, experienced, qualified teachers are essential.

Basic secondary school knowledge cannot be gained abstractly; instructional materials and resources that facilitate learning are critical in secondary education. The principal is responsible for ensuring that these resources are available in the school to enhance the teaching and learning process. Teachers' productivity in their workplace can be affected by their work environment,

including the conduciveness of the school environment. The principal, as the chief administrator of the school, is responsible for providing a positive working environment.

The grounds for this study are to examine the impact of principals' administrative roles on teachers' productivity in secondary schools in the Karu Local Government Area of Nasarawa State, Nigeria. Karu Local Government Area in Nasarawa State, North-Central Nigeria, has its headquarters in New Karu. It is bordered by Keffi, the Federal Capital Territory, and Kaduna State. Towns and villages that make up Karu include New Nyanya, Masaka, Maraba, One Man Village, Gidan Zakara, Uke, Auta Balefi, Kuchikau, Nyanya Gwandara, Aso, Gitata, New Karshi, and others. It has an area of 40,000 hectares (400 km²) and a population of about 2 million. The local government is notable for its strategic proximity to the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja. Established in 1996, the area is predominantly inhabited by diverse ethnic groups, including the Gwandaras, Gbagyis, and Gedes. Its proximity to Abuja has spurred urbanization, making it one of the fastest-growing residential areas in Nigeria.

In terms of education, the local government has 24 public secondary schools (Nasarawa State Ministry of Education, Science and Technology website) and 1,300 private schools (Punch Newspaper, September 25th, 2016).

1.2 Statement of the Problem

This study aims to investigate the influence of school principals' administrative roles in promoting teachers' productivity. One of the goals of education, according to the National Policy on Education (NPE) (2013), is to provide quality education. Teachers' productivity is essential for achieving these goals and is often measured by students' academic performance. Many private secondary school teachers in Nasarawa State have been noted for their low work performance, which manifests in their lateness to work, lack of seriousness, poor attendance to classes, reluctance to write lesson notes, lack of devotion to the teaching profession, and several other behaviors that

diminish their instructional productivity. This decline in teachers' productivity has led to poor academic performance in both internal and external examinations, hindering schools from providing quality education. Despite various efforts, such as teacher training, seminars, and workshops organized by the government, NGOs, and schools to improve the quality of teachers' productivity, this issue persists.

As important as this issue is to the educational system, few related studies have been conducted in Karu Local Government Area of Nasarawa State. It is this gap that has prompted the researcher to investigate the impact of the administrative roles of principals on teachers' productivity in secondary schools in the Karu Local Government Area of Nasarawa State.

-1.3 Purpose of the Study

The primary aim of this study is to explore the influence of principals' administrative roles on teachers' productivity within secondary schools in the Karu Local Government Area of Nasarawa State. Specifically, this research seeks to achieve the following objectives:

1. Identify and analyze the key administrative roles of principals that significantly affect teachers' productivity in the region.
2. Investigate the specific impact of principals' communication strategies on enhancing teachers' effectiveness.
3. Assess how the sustainability of instructional materials managed by principals influences teachers' productivity levels.
4. Evaluate the role of principals in fostering a conducive working environment and its effect on teachers' commitment and output.
5. Propose actionable recommendations to enhance teachers' productivity through effective administrative practices by principals

1.4 Research Questions

1. What are the principals' administrative roles that can influence teachers' productivity in Karu L.G.A. of Nasarawa State?
2. What is the influence of principals' communication roles on teachers' productivity?
3. To what extent does the principals' sustainability of instructional materials influence teachers' productivity?
4. What is the influence of principals' promotion of a good working environment on teachers' productivity?
5. What are the ways to improve teachers' productivity through principals' administrative roles?

Research Hypotheses

1. H01 - There is no significant difference in the responses of secondary teachers in private and public schools regarding the impact of principals' communication skills on their productivity.
2. H02- There is no significant difference in the responses of private and public teachers concerning the influence of principals' sustainability of instructional materials on their productivity.
3. H03 - There is no significant difference in teachers' response regarding the impact of principals' promotion of a favourable working environment on their productivity in private secondary schools versus public secondary schools.
4. H04 - There is no significant difference in teachers' responses about methods for enhancing productivity through principals' administrative roles between those in private secondary schools and those in public secondary schools.

1.5 Significance of the Study

The findings of this study may be useful to various groups in Nasarawa State and the country as a whole. To begin with, the study will help principals understand the impact of their administrative roles on teachers' productivity. Specifically, it will help secondary school principals grasp the

effects of their communication skills, provision of instructional materials, and promotion of a good working environment on teachers' productivity. Thus, principals will be informed about what aspects carry more weight in promoting and achieving educational goals.

Moreover, the study will help teachers understand what they ought to do differently and what they need to improve to enhance their productivity, which will ultimately translate to improved academic performance among students. This may take the form of participating in in-service training to improve their skills, attending conferences, cultivating better relationships with colleagues and students, and using appropriate instructional materials.

The findings may also be useful to the state education board, which is tasked with ensuring that schools offer quality education to students. They may recognize their key role in allocating an adequate budget to facilitate the provision of sufficient instructional materials in secondary schools across the state. Similarly, the Ministry of Education may find the study's findings helpful in identifying the needs for school administrators to enhance teachers' productivity through effective supervision, communication, provision of instructional materials, and a conducive work environment.

Furthermore, the State Teachers Service Commission may benefit from the study's findings by gaining insight into how teachers' productivity may be enhanced through effective administrative practices. Educational policymakers may also find the study's findings valuable by understanding the importance of principals' administrative roles in influencing teachers' productivity. This understanding could stimulate effective ways for school principals to communicate, provide instructional materials, and promote a good working environment. Additionally, the decisive actions, behaviors, and practices of school principals may offer policymakers an opportunity to evaluate administrative roles in context and assess the success of these practices.

1.6 Scope of the Study

The study aims to investigate the influence of principals' administrative roles on teachers' productivity in secondary schools in the Karu Local Government Area of Nasarawa State. It will specifically cover discussions on communication skills, provision of instructional materials, and work environment. The study is delimited to the use of descriptive design, random sampling, and structured questionnaires to assess the perceptions of male and female teachers regarding the identified variables in secondary schools in the Karu Local Government Area of Nasarawa State.

1.7 Definition of Terms

* Influence: To have an effect or impact on something.

* **Principal:** This is a school administrator in charge of a secondary school. He/she coordinates the activities of the school.

-* **Administrative roles:** This a secondary school head who oversees the instructional and operational aspects of the school, ensuring that educational goals are met

* **Teacher:** This is a trained individual who influences students gain knowledge and competence.

- **Productivity:** This refers to the effectiveness and efficiency with which teachers perform their educational duties, ultimately leading to desirable student learning outcomes.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

This chapter deals with the review of literature considered important to this study.

The literature review is discussed under the following sub-headings:

- 2.1 Conceptual Framework
- 2.2 Theoretical Framework
- 2.3 Empirical studies using relevant sub-headings
- 2.4 Appraisal of the Reviewed Literature

2.1 Conceptual framework

2.1.1 Concept of principal

The principal is a person vested with the task of coordinating the affairs of a secondary school. The primary function of the principal is to channel the activities of teachers, students and other staff towards the achievement of the school's objectives. According to Glickman, Gordon, and Ross-Gordon (2014), a school principal is a transformative leader who provides vision, direction, and guidance to the entire school community. He is responsible for creating a positive and conducive learning environment, fostering a culture of continuous improvement, and ensuring the overall success of students and staff.

Ogbonnaya (2005) observed that the principal as a member of the institution, oversees the activities of the school. Principals offer helping hands and utilize opportunity to evaluate the performance of the teachers and learners with the sole aim of achieving the educational goal. It is the duty of the principals as an internal supervisor to meet problems that are connected with students' welfare, progress and shortcomings. The principal as an internal supervisor also plays the role of organizing workshops to update teachers' knowledge and competence.

Nwagwu in Ogbonnaya (2005) listed the following areas where principals as administrative school heads may carry out their supervisory roles in the school system which involves organizing the school time table and seeing the day-to-day operation of the school; maintaining the school building, playground, equipment and facilities; coordinating the activities and functions of teachers; managing good working conditions for staff and establishing high morale among teachers; supervising the extra curricula activities of students; maintaining high standard of conducts and discipline in school both among students and staff; controlling and supervising the business aspect of school life; managing the finances of school and applying appropriate checks and balances in financial matters; keeping different types of records for the school for example attendance book, staff record, school finances, school supplies, records of meeting with school boards, log books, register of admission, visitors' book, corporal punishment book, stock book, school dairy, schemes of work and school time-table; maintaining good school-community relationships and participating in community development projects; supervising and helping teachers grow professionally by encouraging teachers to attend in-service training programmes, workshops and refresher courses organized by higher institutions or ministry of education.

2.1.2 Concept of Principals' Administrative Roles

A role is a set of expectations that coworkers and other organization members have for a person carrying out a specific job. In a secondary school, the principal is at the top of the hierarchical system.

According to Bennell (2004), the principal serves as the school's chief executive officer, administrator, instructional leader, and personnel manager in the secondary school for both students and staff. The principal also manages finances and physical facilities. The principal is in charge of preserving excellent ties with the neighborhood and surrounding communities, staying in touch with the local ministry of education, and ensuring that quality control standards are met.

The principal leads, manages the school and performs various tasks that are directed toward the development of the students as required by the ministry of education. The principals' job as the chief operating officer of a school entails carrying out a variety of duties in order to efficiently run the educational system.

2.1.3 Roles of the Principal as an Administrator.

Ibukun (2011) in Mbanefo (2023) classified the leadership functions of school heads into professional and administrative duties.

- Professional Duties: These are duties performed by the school head to accomplish the goals and objectives of the school. The school heads have to personally inspect school records such as Staff attendance book, Class attendance register, Teachers' Lesson Notes, Log book, Visitors' book and others to ensure that they are properly kept.

- Curriculum Planning and Development: The school heads assist teachers in the area of curriculum planning, initiate the introduction of new subjects to be taught and provide the required resources for effective teaching of various subjects in the school. These functions make school heads to have a little knowledge of all the subjects being taught in their schools and be sound educationists.

- Programme planning for the New Session: The principal has the responsibility of examining the existing academic programme in their schools and decide whether to expand, reduce or modify them in the following year. For instance, school's head may decide to expand his/her school academic programme by introducing History as additional subject in the new session.

- Examination Functions: The school heads are the Chief Examination Officers of their schools, they ensure effective supervision of both internal and external examinations in their schools to

prevent examination malpractices. They also have to supply essential materials required for the conduct of examinations particularly the internal ones.

- Recruitment and Development of Teachers: The school heads have to know their teaching staff strength and the number of teachers needed in their schools, and when to make request for additional teachers. After the recruitment of teachers to their schools, they have to orientate them and encourage them to develop themselves through seminars, workshop and on- the-job training.

- Provision of Facilities: The school heads ascertain the facilities required for the effective functioning of their schools and provide them for their staff, and find out from the various unit heads their requisition for stationery, instructional materials, library and laboratory facilities, workshop materials and so on.

- Budgeting Functions: The school heads have to prepare the annual budget of the school with the aid of their bursars and unit heads for the approval of the board of governors and the ministry of education. This budget contains the estimate of revenue and expenditures of the school for the year.

Administrative tasks are related to maintaining an office setting. These duties vary widely from one workplace to another workplace but in education, they include: scheduling appointments, answering phones, greeting visitors, and maintaining organized file systems for the institution and general school system. These include students' welfare: The school heads look after the welfare of the students by providing first aid services, toilets, bathrooms in case of boarding schools, sports field and so on. They must ensure that food sold to their schools is well prepared.

Staff Welfare: The school heads have to cater for the welfare of their staff. They also motivate the staff for effective performance by attending staff ceremonies, such as house warming, weddings, naming and burial ceremonies. Essential welfare services that the school heads could put in place includes staff cooperative society, end of the year party; staff children party and rewards for good performance.

Regular Meetings with Staff and other Bodies: These duties of school heads include holding statutory and special meetings with their staff. Such meetings give the school heads the opportunity to pass instructions to the Staff and take joint decisions on issues pertaining to the schools. The school heads also have to attend meetings of Parents and Teachers' Association, board of governors, teaching service commission, ministry of education and other relevant bodies.

Public Relations Functions: The school heads as the chief public relations officers of their schools have to relate with members of the community and the officials of relevant educational agencies to project good image of their schools.

Clerical Functions: The clerical functions being performed by the school heads include writing official letters to the stakeholders: the parents, teaching service commission. School management boards, public examination bodies and others and filling forms on staff, students and activities of the schools.

Maintenance of School Facilities: It is the responsibility of the school heads to maintain school facilities such as Vehicle, furniture and fittings, equipment, machines and buildings so that they can have long life span.

Staff and Students' Discipline: Some of the problems encountered in Nigerian schools are products of staff and students' indiscipline. The school heads maintain discipline of staff and students by discouraging lateness to school, laziness, and negligence of duties, disobedience, drug abuse examination malpractices and others. However, for the school heads to perform their leadership functions effectively, the situational factors such as personnel, materials and funds must be favourable and conducive for high productivity. The differences between **professional** and **administrative** duties are: professional duties are duties performed to accomplish the goals and objectives of the school e.g. inspection of school records; while administrative duties are those performed for the purpose of maintaining the school e.g. students and staff welfare.

Figure 2.1 : Role of the school Principal

2.1.4 Management Functions

Mbanefo (2023b) outlined the management functions as follows:

Planning is a process of setting objectives and determining what should be done to achieve them. It is a decision-making activity, used by managers to ensure future success and effectiveness of their institutions as well as themselves.

Organizing is a process of combining the work which individuals or groups have to perform with facilities necessary for their execution, to provide the best channels for efficient, systematic and coordinated application of available efforts. Consequently, the management of institutions organizes the resources (the teachers and facilities) and determines the type of persons required to perform each task.

Directing is the process of influencing people to work willingly and zealously towards the achievement of predetermined objectives. It is to show the path and give guidance to complete a task.

Coordinating is a management mechanism that enables managers to bring other members of their team to relate and work harmoniously. In the context of educational institution, coordination for the

educational managers implies ensuring that the various functional or authority levels [namely, the Heads of Departments (HoDs) and Head of Subjects (HoSs) and others, relate with each other and that their activities are harmonized in an effective way.

Evaluating is the procedure for measuring and assessing the achievement of objectives. It provides an insight into strengths and weaknesses and helps to bring about institutional improvements. Evaluation helps in planning for future endeavours as it determines the effectiveness of previous plans for managers as well as others.

2.1.5 Qualities of an effective principal

Effective principals are skilled in the following ways:

Good leadership - A principal's leadership responsibilities include planning, implementing, supporting, advocating, and monitoring. Principals develop their professional community of educators by sharing leadership with teachers and other administrators to ensure that it is a productive atmosphere for learning.

Promotes school safety and orderliness - Effective principals also create a conducive environment for education that is characterized by safety, support, and orderliness.

Relationship-Building - Principals connect with many people on a daily basis. They must be good at building relationships. The foundation of these relationships includes respect and trust.

Caring- Care about the students, staff and the parents.

Strength—Show confidence in the face of challenges. Display fairness and consistency.

Goal Setting - Having a vision and a plan to achieve that vision is one of the most important qualities of a school principal. Principals lead by example, establishing clear goals and expectations while

holding themselves accountable for their actions. Teachers and students will follow the standards being created by their school leaders- developing a culture of excellence that rewards positive achievements. Ultimately, principals must ensure their staff and students have the tools, training, and resources they need.

2.1.6 Concept of Teachers' Productivity

Generally, productivity to any sector would mean increase in output. In the education sector especially for teachers productivity, one would mean better performance from teachers leading to school leavers or graduates who are morally, spiritually, physically and mentally able to fit into the society as well as the labour market (Babalola, 2009). Many Nigerians are anxious about the low level of productivity in all sectors. (FRN, 2004). School productivity invariably refers to the results that a school system is achieving for a given level of inputs. The focus of productivity in education is centered mainly on the output of the teachers in terms of their ability to increase the learning achievement of students through an effective classroom interaction and management.

2.1.7 Attributes of a productive Teacher

The following are some useful traits of a productive educator:

- **Adaptability** -Being adaptable and flexible allows you to flow between different theories of learning and modes of teaching.
- **Empathy** - This is the ability to understand what another person is feeling or experiencing-put simply, putting yourself in another person's shoes. As a teacher, it's vital to practice empathy instead of making assumptions.
- **Patience** - Patience is important both to possess and to model for your students. Having a reserve of patience will make it easier for a teacher to work through each student's unique struggles and challenges, which may be difficult or slow-going to overcome.

- **Engagement** - If a teacher wants to generate engagement and enthusiasm in his class, it's imperative to exemplify this trait. Showing your students an infectious passion for learning - and all the exciting discoveries and hobbies that it can unlock for them.

- **Active Listener** - Active listening is vital if a teacher wants to effectively diagnose and help overcome students' unique obstacles and challenges.

- **Lifelong Learning** - Productive teachers aren't just interested in teaching — they also have a passion for lifelong learning, which is reflected in their enthusiasm and engagement as instructors. Continued learning and professional development deliver invaluable insight, keeping professionals “sharp” and reminding teachers of the real-world challenges that their students may be facing.

- **Free of Bias** - As a teacher, you'll be responsible for teaching an extraordinarily wide range of students. To combat inequality and discrimination and ensure fairness, you need to assess your students' needs in a way that is free from bias — something that requires you to continuously check in with your own judgments and assumptions about others.

- **Respectful Attitude** - Even in classrooms of adult learners, there's still an inherent imbalance of power that exists between students and teachers. It's imperative for educators to be mindful of this imbalance and ensure that students feel respected and heard for the people they are and what they contribute to the classroom.

- **Creativity** - Creativity goes hand in hand with adaptability — another key trait we explored on this list. Whether you teach first graders or doctoral students, you'll need the ability to innovate, think outside the box, and find novel solutions to challenges, which will empower you to meet a wider range of students' needs. Being creative as an educator will also help you to foster creativity in your students — an essential skill they'll need for countless career paths.

- **Collaborative** - Education is an intensely collaborative field by nature. It involves a constant interplay between students, teachers, administrators, and family members.

- **Promote a Growth Mindset** - Individuals with a fixed mindset perceive intelligence as being determined early in life, which can cause obstacles or challenges to seem insurmountable or overwhelming. In contrast to a fixed mindset, individuals who have a growth mindset believe that traits like intelligence and creativity can be developed with practice.

- **Disciplined** – A productive teacher must be one that is well disciplined and also instills discipline on students.

2.1.8 Reasons for Low Teacher Productivity in Schools

The key reasons for low teacher Productivity in Schools are as follows:

- Low wages when compared with other professionals
- Low status in the society;
- Lack of career advancement opportunities;
- High student-teacher ratio;
- Poor work environment;
- Inadequate fringe benefits and
- Irregular payment of teachers' salaries.

According to various literatures, these conditions are responsible for low teachers' morale and productivity and the difficulty in attracting and retaining quality personnel into the teaching profession. According to Dr. Owusu (The Punch Newspapers, 2004), who once led the accreditation team of the National Commission for Colleges of Education, he remarked that the teaching profession in Nigeria has been relegated to the background and that teaching is not accorded the respect it deserves. A major finding in a study by Kazeem (1999) is that, teachers and other school workers

tend to remain contented and reasonably motivated as long as salaries are paid on time and they are promoted regularly. Much earlier, Eton (1984) also identified the payment of salaries, allowances and promotion as the key factors that shape teachers' attitudes towards their work. Similarly, Amadi (1983) also concluded that the irregular payment of salaries is one of the major problems facing the teaching profession in Nigeria. According to Adelabu (2005), another major source of teachers' dissatisfaction in Nigeria arises from disparities between the teaching profession and other professions such as nursing, with respect to the time and mode of payment of salaries, fringe benefits, promotion prospects and working conditions. However, no consensus exists on the extent to which financial inducements are the really critical motivators. Research has shown that monetary reward itself has not improved teachers' low esteem and their productivity. It was therefore not a surprise when Akinwumi (2000) and Ejiogu (1990) found that what the typical low income earning teacher yearns for is a sizeable salary increase, and they conclude that the payment of a living wage would significantly enhance their commitment and performance. Next to pay is the social status of teachers which has been identified as an important factor impacting teachers' morale and motivation

School leadership and management style are also important factors, which can either motivate or lower teachers' morale and commitment. Nwankwo (1984) found that teachers feel highly motivated when they are consulted about decisions regarding their work. Unfortunately, too high a proportion of school managers (principals and head teachers) are highhanded and autocratic in their dealings with teachers (Ayeni, 2005). The attitude of inspectors towards teachers in supervising their work is another important work-related motivational factor.

2.1.9 Ways of measuring teachers' work productivity in schools

There are many ways to measure teachers' productivity in their teaching jobs, here are let few:

- i. **Carry out observations in the classroom** - Classroom observation is a simple and popular way to gauge a teacher's productivity. An administrator from the school or the external assessor

can both make observations. These observations evaluate teachers' general and subject-specific teaching strategies. These visits may be scheduled or impromptu. It is preferable to carry out surprise observations frequently throughout the year.

ii. **Reporting Your Own Practice** - Teachers are required to provide a self-report on their classroom activities. This report may take the form of interviews, polls, or learning diaries. A teacher's self-report productivity score focuses on broad, all-encompassing facets of teaching, such as classroom observation.

iii. **Assessment by Students** - Teachers and students interact. As a result, they can also offer pertinent data about the effectiveness of teachers. Student evaluation frequently takes the form of questionnaires with Likert scale rating questions. Students may be asked to rate several facets of instructions.

iv. **Conduct a teacher performance evaluation** - A principal or school board can incorporate multiple elements in the evaluation. This helps give teachers a fair chance to demonstrate how effective they are in their jobs and how students are benefitting from their teachings. Annual evaluations are a useful tool for all educators, regardless of how effective they are in their role, because the process provides teachers with useful feedback about their performance.

v. **Establish goals for the evaluation** - Evaluating teachers solely for the purpose of reprimanding them if they don't measure up can have a negative impact on the school staff's productivity. With this mentality, teachers are also unlikely to be receptive to the evaluation process.

Set goals for the evaluation that benefit everyone and look at more than just teacher practice. \

vi. **Define the standard** - To successfully evaluate teachers, there is need to set standard by which they are measured. You can do this by looking at these core values such student development; learning environments; content knowledge; application of content; planning for instruction; teaching strategies; ethical practice and leadership and collaboration.

2.1.10 Factors affecting teachers' work productivity

There are various factors that may influence teachers' productivity. Some of them include principals' communication skills, provision of instructional materials by the school administrator, good work environment, good salary, discipline in school, motivation, Principals' Staff/Students' Personnel Services,

organizational Culture subject knowledge, teaching methods, personal qualities, the classroom environment, general mental ability, personality, relationships with students, preparation and planning, effectiveness in presenting, subject matters, interaction with students and so others. For the purpose of this study, we will be considering five major factors that affect teachers work productivity which are:

- Principals communication skills
- Provision of instructional materials
- Good work environment
- Salary/incentive and
- Discipline

2.1.11 Principal's communication skills and teachers productivity

One of the most important components of human existence is communication. It is an essential aspect of every organization, including schools.

Ndum (2013) defines communication as the effective transmission of common knowledge among people by speaking, writing, or other means. He believed that unless perfect understanding is attained as a result of the transmission of verbal or nonverbal signals, communication has not taken place. According to Abanyam (2001), the employment of an effective and efficient communication system is essential for the proper operation of an administrative organization. Even if policies and programs

were changed, he stated that the administrative system would still not work effectively until all organization members were made aware of the organization's goal (the school). Communication is crucial for the smooth coordination of the school's activities and operations. The school's administrator, the principal, has a large network of connections. In addition to the public and the community, he speaks with parents, students, teachers, and other staff (Udoh, 2019).

According to Yalokwu (2002), communication consists of four elements: the sender, the message, the channel, and the recipient.

These elements of communication have an impact on the effectiveness of any organization. Any of these components that have problems may lead to ineffective communication. Oboegbulem and Onwura (2011) contend that effective communication occurs when the message sender and recipient have a similar comprehension of the message's key points. In other words, a relationship between the sender and the recipient of the communication must exist through the appropriate channels in order for someone to respond. He believes that message transmission through channels of communication is the standard practice in an organization (school). It could be a one-or two-way, vertical, horizontal, downhill, upward, or diagonal channel that is formal or informal. According to Ogunu (2000), management is the artful arrangement and use of human and material resources within a given system for the achievement of particular objectives. It's a conscious process that involves organizing, planning, directing, communicating, and regulating all material and human resources in order to achieve educational goals. Effective communication promotes school efficiency and helps the institution achieve its educational goals.

2.1.12 The school principal's role as a communicator

A principal's role as a communicator can be seen as an extension of the role of a teacher in classroom communication. Like teachers, principals often initiate conversations and facilitate them as others add their ideas, suggestions, and questions. This means they can take the lead in developing and maintaining good relationships at every level, including between teachers, students, and families.

Figure 2.2 – Channels of communication in school. Source: Online Images

2.1.13 Communication tips for school principal

Here are a few communication techniques and tips to help improve school principals' communication:

- **Leverage available technology**- It is important to use technology to our advantage. There are many apps for educators and for schools that can make communications faster, easier, and more secure for all parties involved. Texting parents is particularly useful when teaching in a remote school or virtual learning setting. It does not only keep parents updated on their student's daily studies but also helps get them more involved in their children's learning journey.

- **Send brief and clear messages** - It's best to keep communications brief, clear, and at a low-reading level. This will help ensure everyone who receives the message can understand and read it well.

Provide only the basic and most important information then encourage teachers and parents to contact the school or the principal personally for any clarifications.

- **Create a communications plan each year** - Measuring and evaluating how each form of communication did over the past year can serve as a guide for how to set up the new communication plan for the next school year. Evaluation is essential to find out which channels of communication are most beneficial.

- **Take a collaborative approach** - Communication is a two-way street. Taking a collaborative approach will produce greater results than one person taking on the responsibility for a school-wide communications plan. Working closely and communicating well with representatives from the school community will ensure that multiple levels or groups can voice out their opinions.

Learning is only truly accomplished when clear, timely, and effective communication occurs at all levels. Here are some best practices to ensure effective communications between principals, teachers and students:

- **Communicate with empathy:** Especially when imparting bad news.

Match words to actions: This refers to maintaining integrity as a school leader. As the principal, it is important to stay true to what you say to teachers and students.

- **Become a role model for proper communication:** The best way to encourage clear and consistent communication between all parties in any educational institution is for the head to take the lead and show how teachers, staff, and students should act.

- **Take advantage of open, secure, two-way communication:** Effective communication should always be a two-way thing. Respond to messages promptly and directly. Neglecting to do so may dissuade teachers from further communications with the principal.

2.1.14 Instructional materials and teachers' work productivity

Instructional materials are items or devices that assist the teacher to present a lesson to the learners in a logical manner. They are materials used to facilitate learning for better results. It is the use of the chalkboard, charts, models, overhead projectors, films, television and computers in the teaching process. They are visual, audio and audio –visual devices that help to make abstract concepts and ideas concrete in the teaching and learning process.

Isola (2010) also described instructional materials as objects or devices that assist the teacher to present their lessons logically and sequentially to the learners. Abdu-Raheem (2014) acknowledged that instructional materials are such used by teachers to aid explanations and make learning of subject matter understandable to students during teaching/learning process. Examples of instructional materials are charts, maps, diagrams, comics, models, globes, slides, film strips, television, radio cassettes, video, recorders public address systems, laboratories, and museums, flash cards, flannel boards, card boards, calendar, computer and so on.

Agina – obu (2005) submitted that instructional materials of all kinds appeal to the sense organs during teaching and learning. Section 10 of the National Policy on Education (2004) highlighted the objectives of instructional materials as to; enhance teaching and improve the competence of teachers, make learning more meaningful to students, and develop the effective use of innovative materials in schools. This is to show that, the teacher alone cannot provide all necessary conditions for effective teaching and learning to occur. Thus, other supporting materials must be utilized. This is because students learn and assimilate better when most of the senses are appealed to by the instruction and the use of instructional materials provides the required sensory experiences needed by the learners for an effective and meaningful behavioral change.

2.1.15 Importance of instructional materials in educational system

Osuji (2016) listed them as follows:

- i. They creates conducive environment for teaching and learning.

- ii. They help the learners to develop skills through extra-curricular activities.
- iii. They motivate the school teachers in the execution of their duties.
- iv. They help in the retention of teachers through friendly teaching environment.
- v. They help to reduce vices, truancy and drop-outs among learners.
- vi. They give room for researchers to carry out research.
- vii. They enhance the activities of teaching and learning.
- viii. They make room for continuity in education.
- ix. They help to reduce the fear of insecurity in the school environment.
- x. They give job satisfaction to teachers.
- xi. They help in the actualization of educational goals.

2.1.16 Types of instructional materials

- Visual Aids - Visual aids in teaching are the kind of material that we can see with our eyes. This includes Model, Image, Projector, Slides and Films,
- Audio Aids - Some students are auditory learners, and such students benefit from audio aids in teaching. This includes radio, telephone, teleconferencing, and tape recorders.
- Audio-Visual Aids- These are teaching tools or materials that use both sound and visuals to help in learning. They include Television, Computers etc.
- Tactile Aids- These are tangible objects we can touch and feel.
- Traditional Teaching Aids - Traditional teaching aids, as the name suggests, are the oldest & the most common types of teaching resources. They include blackboards, books, maps, globes, etc.
- Real-Life Aids - These are examples of real-life aids. For instance, when you visit a park, you notice fountains, trees, and plants which can enhance your focus and learning, in this way, you learn through real-life aids.

- Interactive Aids – Example are quizzes, games, or fun activities which enhance children’s learning experience and make them enjoy the session.

Figure 2.3. Types of Instructional materials. Source: Online Images

2.1.17 Effects of instructional materials on secondary school students

Instructional materials are essential and significant tools needed for teaching and learning in the following ways: They promote teachers efficiency and improve students’ performance. They make learning more interesting, practical, realistic and appealing. They also enable both teacher and students to participate actively and effectively in lesson sessions. They give room for acquisition of skills, knowledge and development of self-confidence and self-actualization. The principal should select instructional materials that are not too difficult nor too easy so that students do not feel frustrated or bored. He should be able to know how to determine students’ personal interest and the goals of the school.

2.1.18 Work environment and teachers’ productivity

The success of any organization is closely tied to the job performance of its employees (Mohammed, 2014). Thus, the quality of workplace environment has impact on employees’ motivation level as

well as their performance (Ajala, 2012). Oludeyi (2015) noted that work environment is the settings, situations, conditions and circumstances under which people work. This involves policies, laws, community, resources, working relationships, workplace and internal and external environmental factors, all of which impact the way workers conduct their work functions. In addition, workplace environment factors such as well-ventilated staffrooms and classrooms, teaching aids and instructional materials, workplace reward, management/leadership skills, training etc play an important role towards employees' performance. This is corroborated in the findings of Nanzushi (2015) that work environmental factors that enhance employee performance were physical environmental factors, such as reward, management/leadership style, training and development and work-life balance. However, the findings further reveal the dissatisfaction of employees in the study due to management style and promotions in their organization. This shows that workplace environmental factors have an immense impact on employees' performance either towards positive or negative outcomes.

2.1.19 Factors promoting good working environment

- i. Motivation - The term motivation describes why a person does something. It is the driving force behind human actions. It represents the complex forces and needs which provide the energy for an individual to perform a particular task. A motivated employee is always conscious of the goal to be achieved and directs his efforts towards attaining it. Mullins (2007) noted some factors that affect work motivation and this include individual differences, job characteristics, and organizational practices. Thus, individual differences are the personal needs, values, and attitudes, interests and abilities that people bring to their jobs. Whereas, job characteristics are the aspects of the position that determine its limitations and challenges, whereby,
- ii. Organizational Culture - Organizational culture is a system of shared beliefs about what is important, feeling and relationships in an organization. (Purcell, Kinnie, Swart, Rayton &

Hutchinson, 2008). Bullach, Lunenburg and Potter (2012) noted that knowing the culture of an organization allows employees to understand both the organization's history and current methods of operations which foster commitment to the organization's philosophy and values as well serves as a control mechanism to channel behaviours towards desired behaviors.

iii. Organizational Commitment - Organizational commitment is a situation whereby an employee is in line with a specific organization as well as with the goals and wishes to maintain membership in the organization (Robbins & Judge, 2007). Organizational commitment affects working behaviours of employees such as their observable attitudes and their involvement in professional groups. This support the study of Oludeyi (2015) which stated that highly committed staff will perform better on the job and would not exhibit negative behaviour in workplace.

iv. Teacher Commitment - Yusuf and Metiboba (2012) describe teacher commitment as a physiological state which characterizes the teacher's relationship with the organization and has implications for a teacher to continue or discontinue their membership in the organization. The commitment therefore entails attitude or orientation of teachers towards the organization which links or attaches the teachers to the organization. These authors further noted that teacher's commitment is a process whereby the goals of the individual or worker are increasingly integrated with that of the organization. Teacher commitment entails three components – workers' readiness to exert effort on behalf of the school; workers acceptance of school goals and workers desire to remain in the school.

Figure 2.4 – Working Environment. Sources: Online Images

2.1.20 The school environment and teachers’ productivity

Mbanefo (2023), postulate that the school environment has a great impact on students' learning and growth, which includes significant aspect of their ethical, social and emotional development. A conducive school environment is supportive and caring to students which directly discourage them to be involved in substance abuse, violence and related behaviours. The geographical location of a school has significant influence on the academic performance of students and the development of a nation in general. Mudassir, Norsuhaily and Ado (2015) concurred to this position, when they reported that the school environment that significantly influences students' academic performance is a school with adequate learning facilities, good teacher-student relationship and favourable learning environment.

Figure 2.5 – Dimensions of school environment. Source : Dynamics of Educational Administration and Planning of Institutions (Mbanefo 2023)

The above figure represents the components and various dimensions of a school environment.

These dimensions are academic dimension; physical dimension and the social dimension.

The social dimension of school environment includes: Quality of interpersonal relationships between and among students, teachers, and other staff; equitable and fair treatment of students by teachers and staff; degree of competition and social comparison among students; degree to which students, teachers, and staff contribute to decision-making at the school.

The academic dimension includes: Quality of instruction; learning objectives, students learning outcomes, teacher expectations for student achievement; and monitoring of student progress and promptly reporting results to students and parents.

The physical dimension includes: Appearance of the school building and its classrooms (beautification-aesthetics); school size and ratio of students-to-teachers in the classroom, classrooms organization/dynamics in the school; availability of resources including health care system. Students and staff personal security and safety in the school (Mbanefo, 2019b)

2.1.21 Influence of work environment on teachers' productivity

Work environment significantly influences teacher productivity. Committed teachers who are highly motivated in terms of conducive work environment contribute their time and energy to the pursuit of school goals and are increasingly acknowledged being the primary asset available to the school. Furthermore, teachers who share a commitment to the school and their collective wellbeing are more suitable to generate the social capital that facilitates school learning. Therefore, un-conducive work environment creates a feeling of not being fulfilled and may affect their input in the organization (Ushie et al, 2015). As such, a positive work environment make teachers' feel good about coming to work and this provides the motivation to sustain and increase commitment (Ali, Ali & Adan, 2013). Thus if a worker fails to find his fulfillment and satisfaction, it could lead to boredom, reduced efficiency, fatigue, frustration and dependency, which leads to low commitment.

2.2.22 Good salary and teachers' work productivity

Basic salary is a regular monthly payment for non-manual employees that is typically expressed in annual terms and does not typically include productivity enhancements. Wages are payments made to manual laborers that are always based on hourly or piece rates.

According to Surbhi (2015), a salary is a specific sum of money that is given to employees on a monthly basis in exchange for their performance and output.

He continued by saying that while salary earners are typically described as doing "white collar office jobs," this terminology indicates that they are well-educated, skilled, and employed by an organization, as well as holding a respectable status in society. Performance and pay have a strong correlation.

Teachers' commitment and motivation is largely tied to their pay. The benefit package for Nigerian teachers is among the worst in the nation despite the fact that they have the huge duty of shaping Nigeria's future. Because of their pitifully low pay, Nigerian teachers lack motivation. Lack of motivation has made some to leave the profession.

The teachers' turnover rate in education sector is higher than any other sectors (Liu & Meyer, 2005). Due to the constant teacher turnover, there are now insufficient qualified teachers to serve the growing student populations. Poor teachers' performance causes schools to face a number of issues, including low student satisfaction, student turnover intentions, the expense of employing new staff, and delays in the delivery of instruction. Paying teachers well helps keep them on the job and perform well. Researchers discovered that the primary predictor of teacher attrition and turnover was low pay. Since several studies have revealed that poor incomes were the biggest predictor of teacher turnover and poor performance behaviors, a good or rise in teacher remuneration may lower teachers' inclinations to leave the profession and improve their commitment in the profession (Liu, 2007; Loeb et al., 2005).

MySalaryScale conducted a survey in August 2017 to gain information about the pay of teachers in Nigeria. The average compensation of teachers ultimately came out to be incredibly low. It was also upsetting and not very inspiring. It was discovered that Nigerian public schools teachers made an average income of ₦49,000 per month while some in the private schools earn as low as ₦20,000.

Further research revealed that these teachers continue to make an average income of ₦59,000 even after they have worked there for many years, perhaps ten years or more as senior level personnel. This is merely typical. Some teachers in Nigeria make considerably more money than this, while some earn less. A typical teacher has a low level of living, earns a pitiful salary, and rarely gets paid on time.

Teachers in Nigeria, appear dissatisfied with their remuneration and perceive themselves as poorly paid in comparison with similarly qualified staff in other occupations (Sango, Nyatanga and Saruchera, 2016). If teachers are asked what might be done to encourage them to work harder and to improve the quality of their work, their first suggestion is likely to be to raise their salaries. The performance of teachers can be seen in their enthusiasm to work, the academic performance of the students, their attendance, and even in their behavior in performing their work. Salary is one of the major motivation tool which the principal should use to improve the performance of his teacher. Ssegawa (2019) observed that salary increment enhances teachers' commitment, performance and productivity rate. Nwosu (2017) also emphasized the importance of reward in motivating the performance of teachers.

The salary increment of teachers in secondary schools will improve the commitment of teachers which in turn will improve the performance of teachers, reduce the turn-over rate of teachers and improve their productivity.

2.2.23 Students' discipline and teachers' work productivity.

Jade (2023) defined discipline as a system of rules for managing behaviour and maintaining order. In a school context, discipline refers to the practices and policies school administrators and staff members implement to manage student conduct. Discipline is the process of bringing out the life of the student, teacher, value of the school and the community at large. The school head has it as part of his responsibility to carry out disciplinary actions in the school for the reputability of his school. If the teachers are not committed to teaching or do not have intrinsic satisfaction, they may be a source of indiscipline in the school. There are cases of rape, examination malpractice, bullying,

insubordination, theft, fighting, gossip and disobedience, rejection of transfer and abuse of school properties.

2.2.24 Importance of school rules and regulations in curbing indiscipline in School.

School rules are guidelines and expectations set by educational institutions to ensure a safe and productive learning environment. These rules provide structure and guidance for students, helping them understand what is expected of them both academically and behavioural. By following these rules, students can navigate their school environment with confidence and clarity. One of the primary purposes of school rules is to instil discipline in students and promote safe and inclusive learning environment. The following are importance of school rules and regulations: School rules and regulations provide structure and guidance for student behavior, contributing to a safe and productive learning environment. Adherence to school rules fosters social-emotional development, teaching students important skills such as cooperation, respect, and empathy.

Following school rules enhances self-discipline, responsibility, and an understanding of the consequences of one's actions. Understanding and following school rules and regulations leads to academic success, a sense of belonging, and improved social-emotional well-being. Obeying school rules and regulations also fosters self-discipline and responsibility. When students understand the consequences of their actions and the importance of following rules, they develop a sense of accountability. This self-discipline extends beyond the school setting and can positively impact their personal and professional lives in the future. Moreover, school rules and regulations contribute to the development of empathy and respect for others. By following rules that promote inclusivity and fairness, students learn to appreciate and value the perspectives and experiences of their peers. This understanding of diversity and respect for others is crucial for building strong relationships and creating a harmonious community.

2.2.25 A sample of a school rules and regulations

Nasarawa state government (2010) outline the following as rules and regulations guiding discipline

and conduct of students in post primary institutions in the state:

Punctuality: Late coming is an offence that deserves punishment. All learners must be in school before 7:30am.

Dressing: - All learners must dress in the prescribed and authorized school uniforms. Boys must tuck in their shirts, no sagging, no pencil trouser or any other now-a day's fashion.

Grooming: - All boys are expected to have low haircuts (skinny or clearance), no outlandish hair style like Gallas, Punk, Round cut, Afro, Zig-zag, Dye cut, Tim park, Sporting waves, Dread locks (dada), Nike, Shedding etc is allowed. Girls in modest hair styles, trimmed nails and no painting of nails, lips or face. Marking of tattoo on the body is highly prohibited.

Fighting & bullying: - Fighting and bullying are punishable in the school.

Calling of names: - Call each other by names known for. No imposing of nick name. Any form of verbal abuse on any student is a punishable offence

Reporting and inviting parents to school: - Reporting to parents and inviting parents to the school by students without clearance from school authority is a serious offence.

Immoral relationship: - Anyone caught in questionable, illicit or immoral relationship with a student or teacher shall face the wrath of the school.

Loitering: - No student should be seen loitering during school hours. Only one student may leave a class at a time.

Stealing: - Stealing is repugnant to the norms of the society. It is a shameful offence. Anyone caught faces severe disciplinary action.

Pregnancy: - Any female student who gets pregnant has naturally dismiss herself from the school.

Selling and buying: - No learner is allowed to sell or buy any item from a fellow learner within the school compound.

Writing/painting/cartooning: - No learner is allowed to write/draw/paint on the wall desk or board without permission.

Use of toilet: - Students must not defecate/urinate in an unauthorized place. The toilet is the only approved place for easing oneself.

Littering: - All pieces of papers/dirt must be dropped in the waste baskets. Littering is an offence that attracts punishment.

Breaking of lockers & chairs etc: - School properties must be treated with respect. Students who commits such offence are liable to buy new ones.

Body cleanliness: - All learners must keep their bodies impeccably clean. A clean student is a healthy student.

Smoking/use of alcohol: - These are serious offences. Remember that the Federal Ministry of health warns that cigarette smoking is dangerous to health, and smokers are liable to die young. Therefore, any student caught whether within the school or outside the school will be disciplined.

Use of pornographic materials: - No learner is allowed to possess, share, distribute, handle, watch or read any pornographic literature/material. Anyone caught will face the wrath of the school.

Cult membership:- No learner should become a member of a cult/secret society/questionable club or group. Any intimidation to join by any one should be reported. It is dangerous to the well-being of any student or family. It is a very serious offence that may attract expulsion.

Possession of dangerous weapon:- Any learner found in possession of dangerous weapon of any kind, will be seen as an unfriendly fellow and treated accordingly.

Demonstration & riots:-Rioting is a scandalous way of showing indiscipline. Students should not engage in riots, demonstration or rampage. Such offence deserves severe punishment.

Use of bell:- Only the school bell ringers or regulators are allowed to handle the school bell. Any unauthorized person may attract disciplinary measures.

Exam behaviour:- Examination is the focal point in any education system. Therefore, learners must respect exam in whatever form, be it tests, assignments, projects or quiz. Any form of exam malpractice like stealing of answer scripts, impersonation, collusion, girraffing, bringing in foreign materials in the exam hall, smuggling of question paper/answer script, swapping of scripts, comparing of answers, use of social media gadgets to aid exam mal practice etc must be avoided. Any culprit may be punished appropriately.

Harassment of staff:- Any learner who harasses a member of staff will face immediate suspension or expulsion.

2.2.26 List of offences punishable in secondary schools

Nasarawa state government (2010) outlined the following as offences and the punishments applicable to students in post primary institutions in the state which include:

1. Absenteeism 2. Lateness to school 3. Disobedience/Insubordination 4. Entry into unauthorized places; 5. Non-attendance to classes/duties; 6. Trespassing; 7. Abuse of toilets; 8. Littering; 9. Bad use of language; 10. Improper dressing; 11. Improper grooming; 12. Jumping of walls; 13. Bullying; 14. Calling of names; 15. Fighting; 16. Reporting to parents/inviting parents to school without clearance from school; 17. Non-payment of school fees; 18. Loitering; 19. Leaving school before school over; 20. Stealing; 21. Pregnancy; 22. Buying and selling; 23. Writing/painting/cartooning on the wall; 24. Uncleanliness of Body; 25. Improper waste disposal; 26. Failure to take part in school work; 27. Smoking; 28. Use of alcohol; 30. Use of drugs/drug abuse; 31. Use of phonographic materials; 32. Membership of secret society; 33. Possession of dangerous weapon; 34. Taking part in demonstrations/riots; 35. Inciting others; 36. Unauthorized harvesting of fruits in the school; 37. Abuse of opinion box; 38. Indebtedness to the school; 39. Unauthorized ringing of the school bell; 40. Offences in the Boarding House and examination malpractice

2.2.27 Punishments applicable to students for breaking school's rules

1. Canning 2, Grass Cutting 3. Kneeling Down 4. Digging of ditches 5. Sweeping 6. Picking of litters 7. Scrubbing of floors 8. Stumping 9. Suspension 10. Writing of apology letter and reading it before all students 11. Seizing of property 12. Corporal punishment 13. Denial of privileges 14. Striping of prefect ship 15. Expulsion

2.2 Theoretical Framework

2.2.1 The Administrative Management Theory

The administrative theory is a classical management theory. The chief proponents of this theory are Henri Fayol (1841-1925), Luther Gulick (1892), and Lyndall Urwick (1943). One of the earliest management theories and one of the most significant management theories is claimed to be Henry Fayol's Administrative Management Theory. The popularity and wide adoption of Henri Fayol's management principles led to him being called the —father of modern management. He is today regarded as one of the most important contributors to the current notion of management, thanks to his work on the Principles of Management and the Primary Functions of Management. Henri Fayol presented the "14 principles of administration" in 1916 as a result of his wealth of experience and several research projects. These ideas then appeared in his book *Administration Industrielle et Générale* in 1917. (Fayol, 1917; 1930). The administrative management theory focuses on how to interact with and manage employees. This theory advocates for a formalized administrative structure, the delegation of power and division of labor. From this theory, it can be deduced that for efficient and improved performance of teachers, principals and administrators have to pay more attention to the division of work, clear definition of duties and responsibilities and maintaining specialization and coordination.

2.2.2 The Scientific Management Theory

This theory was propounded by Fredrick Winslow Taylor (1890-1940). Taylor believed that improving employee practices was the greatest approach to boost organizational output. These ideas presented employees as machines that their managers could control. The needs of the organization are the focus of the leader in this situation. Taylor thought that through rigorous analysis, managers and employees might come together to form a cohesive group that would work for their mutual advantage.

The theory operated under the presumption that identifying the "One-best- way" was all that was required to carry out organizational tasks and to reward those who followed organizational standards. Scientific management theory is crucial since every business operation around the world is affected by its influence and management philosophy.

According to Grimsley (2003), scientific management theory aimed to increase an organization's efficiency through employing scientific, engineering, and mathematical analytics. It focuses on ways to boost workers' productivity and efficiency through technical work organization architecture and the provision of financial incentives as the motivator for higher levels of production. Frederick Winslow Taylor, known as the father of Scientific Management, proposed four guiding principles to improve efficiency and productivity in the workplace. These principles are:

1. **Develop a Science for Each Element of Work:** Replace rule-of-thumb methods with scientific study and analysis of tasks to determine the most efficient way to perform each job.
2. **Scientifically Select, Train, Teach, and Develop the Worker:** Carefully select workers based on their abilities and scientifically train them to perform their tasks efficiently.
3. **Cooperate with the Workers:** Foster a collaborative environment where management and workers work together to ensure that tasks are performed according to the developed scientific methods.
4. **Divide the Work and Responsibility:** Clearly define roles and responsibilities between management and workers, ensuring that each group focuses on their specific tasks to maximize efficiency.

These principles aim to enhance productivity and create a harmonious relationship between workers and management. According to this theory, a manager should specify how a particular tasks should be carried out by school staff, the steps that should be taken to complete the work, the amount of time

needed to complete the work using various methods, and the most efficient way to complete schoolwork.

2.2.3 Human Relations Theory

The father of human relations theory is regarded as being Elton Mayo. He discussed how human behavior affects production while emphasizing the value of management and employee communication. The experiments Professor Elton Mayo and his Harvard School of Business colleagues conducted at the Hawthorne Works of the Western Electric Company, close to Chicago, led to the development of this theory. An important turning point in the evolution of management theory was the Hawthorne Experiments. In order to improve their interactions with their employees, many corporations began to take action. The managers were asked to assume a new position and develop innovative ideas of authority, motivation, and leadership. The human relations theory was founded on the idea that management needed to consider the affairs of the person performing the task in addition to figuring out the best technological ways to increase organizational output. The main tenet of the human relations movement was that, as administration entails working with and through people, attention should be placed on interpersonal and intra-personal aspects of managing people while managing organizational affairs.

From the human relations movement, the following ideas can be drawn:

For the benefit of everybody, educational administrators should foster partnerships among team members. It is thought that strong staff morale and harmony are necessary for enhanced teaching and learning. Educational administration should be viewed as a service activity that supports successful educational initiatives; it should not be perceived as a goal in and of itself. The importance of participatory decision-making among administrators should be emphasized more.

2.2.4 - The Path Goal Theory

This theory was developed by Robert J. House (1971) and modified in 1996. House believed that a leader's behaviour is dependent on the fulfillment, motivation and performance of his or her subordinates. The Path Goal Theory states that a good leader equips subordinates with clear direction, sets high goals, gets involved in goal achievement and supports his employees. The leader clears the path for the followers to take. Dixon and Hart (2010) points out that path-goal theory advocates for senior leaders possessing attributes such as having a flexible behaviour, giving clear and precise instructions, provision of direction, instituting a solid structure, and rewards in order to have improved performance amongst the juniors. According to this theory, leaders should clarify the path to subordinates such that they know which way to go and remove barriers that are stopping them from going there (House, 1971)

Path Goal theory is relevant to this study as it perceives the nature of leadership as a key influencer to the performance of the subordinates.

The theory posits that through good leadership, senior leaders encourage and lead the subordinates to contribute towards the effectiveness and success of the organization of which they are members. (McShane & Glinow, (2010). This theory includes four different approaches of leadership behaviour applicable in schools which are participative, supportive, directive and achievement-oriented (Alanazi, Khalaf & Rasli, (2013). Participative leadership is geared towards encouraging innovation and creativity through collection of new ideas for institutional effectiveness. Supportive approach by the principal motivates the staff through building strong emotional bonds and improving trust relationships. Principals use a directive approach in encouraging staff working abilities through planning and organizing staff development activities. Lastly, an achievement-oriented approach can be utilized by the principal through establishing high quality targets for staff and seeking improvement over time. A school principal motivates teachers to fill learning gaps in order to

improve their performance. The principal influences the teacher's attitudes by setting challenging goals with high expectations and high standards for improved performance. These approaches by the school principal reduce conflicts, dissatisfaction and stress in the workplace. The school administrator motivates teachers by sharing responsibilities, removing obstacles, providing good working relationships, supporting their working morale, decreasing task boredom and pushing for job performance (Olowoselu, bin Mohamad & Mohamed, 2019). This theory also informs the study as leaders employ behavior that eliminates deficiencies and is instrumental to employees' satisfaction, as well as individual working performance. The theory consequently recognizes the impact of a leader on the achievement of goals (Malik, 2012).

The principal should increase confidence while at the same time decrease the anxiety of teachers through administrative support. This theory links to this study as it postulates that leader's behaviour determines the performance of their subordinates. In the context of this study, the interaction between principal, teachers and the school culture is paramount to improve teacher's skills and knowledge. A school principal who supports teachers through supervision, professional development, motivates and delegates duties to teachers ensures school success as teachers are motivated. Teachers are satisfied as they develop themselves to improve on their knowledge and teaching techniques. As a result, teachers gain expertise and self-confidence in work development (Olowoselu, bin Mohamad & Mohamed, 2019).

2.3 Empirical Studies

The following related empirical studies were reviewed:

A study carried out by Adegbesan (2013) investigated why some principals prefer to embrace certain leadership styles and the effect of such styles on the teachers' attitude to work. The purpose of this study was to investigate how principals' leadership styles effects teachers' attitude to work. The study had three research questions and four hypotheses which centered on the leadership role of the

principals. The study adopted the descriptive research design. The random sampling technique was used to draw a sample of 45 teachers and 56 principals from the secondary schools in Abeokuta South Local Government Area. Structured questionnaire and interview were used to elicit information from the respondents. The questionnaire adopted the four point rating, which enabled respondents to indicate the extent of agreement or disagreement with the questionnaire items. The data collected were subjected to a number of statistical analyses, including frequency counts and percentages, t-test and Chi-square tests. The findings of the study revealed that the administrative styles adopted by the principals of secondary schools in Abeokuta South Local Government Area were found to be inadequate for effective school administration. The personality traits exhibited by the principals appeared somewhat harsh to their subordinates. Teachers in these schools were not adequately motivated and encouraged to carry out their duties. Based on the above findings it is recommended that principals in Abeokuta South Local Government Secondary Schools should not see themselves as all in all. They should involve their subordinates when taking vital decisions. There should be free flow of information in the schools. The work has implication for policy and practice of secondary education in Abeokuta South Local Government Area. The study under review is a thorough one; because it is looking at some of the functions of the principal in secondary school which includes administration and coordination of the activities of the school, provision of instructional materials, principals' communication skills and promoting good work environment. It is also concerned with the behaviour teachers expect the principals to put up. The present study is similar to the study under review in the sense that both try to look at the outcome of principals' roles as it affects the teachers job performance. In terms of location, the study reviewed was carried out in Abeokuta South Local Government Area while the present study is being done in Karu local government area of Nasarawa State, Nigeria.

Nkwoh Kelechukwu (2011), carried out a research titled "The administrative roles of private secondary school principals in Aba zone of Abia State". It is a survey research and it adopted seven research questions that guided the study. The objectives of the research were to determine the

principals' role in effective management of the financial and school business administration, students' personnel administration, staff personnel administration, instruction and curriculum development and in general tasks. Sample of six hundred and sixteen (616) respondents" was chosen from group of teachers of schools. The six hundred and sixteen respondents were selected by stratified, random proportionate techniques across Aba education zone of Abia State. The instrument used to collect data is a 35- item questionnaire on Principal Administrative tasks Performance Evaluation Question (PATPEQ) which was based on Likert's 4- point scale-I lightly Effective. Moderately effective and Not Effective- was used to collect data. The result was analyzed using mean and standard deviation. The result revealed that principals were moderately effective in financial and school business administration, students" personnel administration, staff personnel administration, instruction and curriculum development and in general tasks. The principals were effective in school-community relation and they were not effective in school plants. Based on the discussions and conclusions, the researcher made some of the following recommendations on the way forward. The selection of principal should be done based on certain criteria which are logically laid down by the state education board and made available to prospective principals. There is need for regular seminars and workshop for private secondary school principals on principal's administrative roles, the principals should also be sensitized on how to show concern to staff and build cohesive work groups for the achievement of the educational goals. Similarity, the present study lies in the fact that both studies were concern with the administrative and leadership roles of secondary school principals. Also, the location of the study was Abia State, while the present study is being carried out in Nasarawa State, Nigeria.

Kolawole (2011) investigated the instructional supervisory roles of secondary school principals and inspectors of the ministry of education in Lagos State. The objective of the study was to find out the relationship between the instructional supervisory roles of Secondary School Principals and inspectors of the Ministry of Education in Lagos State. A total of 20 principals and 20 inspectors were randomly selected. The descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study which utilized two sets of questionnaire to gather information from the sample chosen for the study. Two

hypotheses were generated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. The data collected were analyzed using Pearson product moment correlation to test the relationship. The study revealed that there was significant relationship between principals and inspectors instructional supervision. The study also showed that principals and inspectors were alert to the possibilities for improvement of instructions, possess the ability to work and actively engaged in discharging their duties in terms of monitoring and evaluation. Based on the findings, it was recommended that the Principals and inspectors should be given more necessary orientation which would guide them the more in their positions as instructional supervisors. The role performance of the principal is not limited to monitoring and evaluation alone but much more as explored by the present study. A dissimilarity in the study reviewed and the present study lies in the location of research. The present study is being taken in Nasarawa State, Nigeria while the study reviewed was carried out in Lagos State, Nigeria.

Sule (2013) investigated the influence of the principal's supervisory demonstration strategy on teachers' job performance in Nigerian secondary schools. The Specific objective of this study was to determine the extent to which the principals' supervisory demonstration strategy influences teachers' job performance. Respondents comprised of 232 teacher and 9,533 students of secondary schools in Cross River State. 660 teachers and 3,300 students selected using the stratified random sampling and the simple random approach make up the sample for the study. Data was collected with Principals' Instructional Supervisory Strategies Questionnaire (PISSQ) and Teachers' Job Performance Scale Questionnaire (TJPSQ). The result of analysis utilizing one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) indicated that principal's demonstration strategy did not significantly influence teachers' job performance. The study recommended that regular supervision should be organized by the Ministry of Education using more robust supervisory strategies which may include classroom visitation and inspection, inspection of teachers' lesson notes, conferencing strategy, inspection of teachers' record keeping, and administrative workshop strategy. This was carried out in Cross River State and it is interested only in the supervisory role of the principal as it relates to teacher and students in terms of his/her demonstrative ability. The present study is being carried out in Karu local

government area of Nasarawa State and it aimed at the impact of principals' administrative roles on teachers' productivity. This make the present study similar.

2.4 Appraisal of the Reviewed Literature

This research work focuses on the impact of principals' administrative roles on teachers' productivity in private schools in Karu local government area of Nasarawa state. From the reviewed literature, it was observed that based on past studies; there is a positive relationship between principals' administrative role and teachers' productivity. It was deduced that teachers' instructional performance is influenced by the administrative and leadership roles of the school Principal. The way that the principal carries out his duties and responsibilities within the school can either promote or discourage the productivity of teachers. It could also be deduced from the reviewed literature that teachers will perform better under the supervision and leadership of competent principals than under incompetent ones.

Having explored several literatures, it was deduced that limited studies have been conducted on the principals' administrative roles on teachers' productivity especially in terms of instructional materials, communication skills, and promotion of good working environment. No any study cited here, was conducted in Karu local government area of Nasarawa state. No study was done with the topic "Impact of principals' administrative roles on teachers' productivity" in Karu local government. The results obtained from a foreign study might not be the same as that of a study carried out locally and therefore the need for a study that is conducted locally to yield results that may be applicable to the immediate environment. The researcher decided to carry out this study in order to fill this gap.

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

This chapter discusses the design and methodology of the research. It includes the research design, population, the sampling techniques employed in arriving at the sample, instrument used to collect the data, validity, reliability of the instrument, procedure for data collection and the method of data analysis.

3.1 Research Design

The research design adopted for this study is the survey research design. This design included the collection of numerical data through questionnaires administered to respondents, in order to find a solution to the research problem. The reason for using survey research design is to assess the respondents' opinions and thoughts on the research problem.

3.2 Population of the Study

The population of the study was made up of all the teachers of secondary schools in Karu Local Government. The study comprised two public schools and 3 private schools.(Government Secondary school Bakin Ado, Government Sec Sch Masaka, Ambassador Sky Pathway Academy, Divine Fortune Int'l Academy and Valliant Private school Ado) A total number of 145 correctly filled questionnaires were returned out of the 150 distributed to the sampled teachers in the selected schools

Table 3.1 - Overview of the total number of schools and teachers in Karu LGA.

	Category	Data
1	Total Number of Public Senior Secondary Schools (GSS/GDSS)	12
2	Total Number of Public Junior Secondary Schools (GJSS)	12
3	Total Number of Registered Private Secondary Schools	600
4	Average Num of Teachers in a Public Senior Secondary Schools	32

5	Average Number of Teachers in a Public Junior Secondary School	15
6	Average Number of Teachers in a Registered Private Sec. Sch.	13
7	Total Number of Teachers in All Public Senior Secondary Schools	384
8	Total Number of Teachers in All Public Junior Secondary Schools	180
9	Total Number of Teachers in All Registered Private Sec. Schools	7800
0	All Number of Teachers in Public/Registered Private Sec Schools	8364

3.3 Sample and Sampling Techniques

For this study, a simple random sampling technique was employed to select five secondary schools from Karu Local Government Area, ensuring that each school had an equal opportunity to be included in the sample. To determine the appropriate sample size for the participants, the Taro Yamane formula was utilized. This statistical formula is commonly used to calculate sample sizes in research, accounting for the total population and the desired level of precision. A sample of 150 teachers was drawn from the selected schools using this formula.

3.4 Instrument for data collection

The instrument used for data collection was a self-developed questionnaire titled: Questionnaire on the impact of principals' administrative roles on teachers' productivity (QIPARTP). It was divided into two (2) sections. "Section A includes the demographic data of the respondents such as sex, age, status, years of experience and name of school. Section B includes the main questions to be answered by the respondents. It is made up of 24 items divided into 5 clusters. The Likert rating scale was used to measure the opinions of the respondents ranging from Strongly Agree (SA) = 4, Agree (A) = 3, Disagree (D) = 2 and strongly disagree (SD) = 1. This enabled the researcher to collect relevant data for the study.

3.5 Validity of the Instrument

To ensure the validity of the research instrument, it was presented to 3 experts in the field (my supervisor, a lecturer of Measurement and Evaluation and an expert from the department of Admin

and Planning, faculty of Education of the University) They checked and modified the items to ensure its validity. This helped in minimizing errors in the instrument.

3.6 Reliability of Research Instruments

Mbanefo (2023b) defined reliability as an index that estimates the trustworthiness or dependability of scores. Thus, "the reliability of a measuring instrument is the degree of constancy with which it measures whatever it is measuring".

The questionnaire was validated and trial tested to obtain the reliability coefficient, which was 0.75 of Cronbachs' Alpha coefficient

Pilot testing was done by administering the instrument to fifteen (15) teachers in Karu LGA in order to ascertain the reliability of the instrument. The pilot study enabled the researcher to assess the clarity of the questionnaire items so that those items that were found to be inadequate were modified to improve the quality of the research instrument thus increasing its reliability.

3.7 Procedure for Data Collection.

After obtaining an approval letter (introduction letter) from the study Centre, a set of questionnaires, letter of introduction and attestation letter were taken to the principals of the five selected schools. Copies of the questionnaire were administered to the teachers. A total of one hundred and fifty (150) questionnaires were distributed to the five (5) schools. Thirty (30) to each school. At the end of the day, one hundred and forty-five (145) correctly completed questionnaires were returned.

3.8 Method of Data Analysis.

The data analysis in this research project involved a systematic approach utilizing descriptive statistics to answer the research questions. The analysis was conducted using SPSS (**Statistical Package for the Social Science**) software, focusing on the computation of means, standard

deviations, and frequency distributions for various response items collected from teachers in Karu L.G.A, Nasarawa State.

To address the research questions, tables were generated that summarized the respondents' perceptions regarding several facets of principals' administrative responsibilities. Each item was assessed on a scale (0 to 4), where the mean scores indicated the level of agreement among respondents.

Additionally, hypothesis testing was employed to determine whether significant differences existed in perceptions between public and private school teachers regarding the impact of various principal behaviors on teachers' productivity. An independence Sample T-test was conducted, and p-values were interpreted, with significance set at the 0.05 level. By synthesizing findings through descriptive statistics and hypothesis tests, the research provided insights into the relationships between principals' roles and teachers' productivity, highlighting areas of agreement and divergence among respondents.

The boundary of responses were calculated by dividing the serial width (4) by the number of responses (5) and was found to be 0.8. This was used to interpret the mean values. The acceptable boundaries for each response is $0 = 0.0 + 0.8$ (not applicable), $1 = 0.8 + 0.8 = 1.6$. (VLE), $2 = 1.6 + 0.8 = 2.4$ (LE), $3.2 - 4.0$ is very High Extent.

Real numbers limits are used to interpret the results based on the following decision rule. For the research questions, any mean between the ranges of 0 0.8 is not applicable; 0.8 to 1.6 is strongly disagree; 1.6 to 2.4 is disagree; 2.4 to 3.2 is agree; 3.2 to 4.0 is strongly agree. This can also be applicable to high extent and low extent responses. The level of significance was $P = 0.05$ level of significance. Conversely, the null hypothesis is rejected when the calculated P values are lower than the $P = 0.05$ level of significance.

CHAPTER FOUR

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

The results of the study are presented in accordance with the research questions and hypotheses.

4.1 Answers to the Research Questions

4.1.1 Research Question 1

4.1.2 Research Question 2

4.1.3 Research question 3

4.1.4 Research question 4

4.1.5 Research question 5

4.2 Test of Hypotheses

4.2.1 Hypothesis 1

4.2.2 Hypothesis 2

4.2.3 Hypothesis 3

4.2.4 Hypothesis 4

4.3 Summary of the Findings

4.1 - Answers to the Research Questions

The research questions were answered by the computation of the descriptive statistics using SPSS and the results were presented in tables.

4.1.1 Research questions 1 : What are the principals' administrative role that can influence teachers' productivity in Karu L.G.A of Nasarawa State?

Table 1 - Frequencies, Means and Standard Deviation of the responses of the respondents on the principals' administrative role that can impact on teachers' productivity in Karu L.G.A of Nasarawa State

N= 145

S/N	Items	Frequency of the response					\bar{x}	SD	Decision
		0	1	2	3	4			
1	Principals' Communication roles can positively enhance teachers productivity	-	-	1	43	101	3.69	.479	S. Agree
2	Provision of Instructional materials generates teacher productivity abilities	-	-	-	81	64	3.44	.498	S. Agree
3	Principals' promotion of good	-	-	1	109	35	3.23	.441	S.

	work environment motivates the teachers to be committed and have positive attitude to work	-								Agree
4	Principals' maintaining of Staff and Students' Discipline promotes teachers' productivity	-	1	54	90	3.61	.503			S. Agree
5	Principals' maintenance of school facilities extend the lifespan and enhance proper utilization of the facilities	-	-	75	70	3.48	.501			S. Agree
6	Principals accountability role activates teachers to yield better result	-	-	-	65	80	3.55	.499		S. Agree
	Cluster						3.50	0.479		

\bar{x} = Means, SD = Standard Deviation, SA = Strongly Agree, A = Agree, SD = Strongly Disagree

The data presented in table 1 above, the mean rating (\bar{x}) and the standard deviation (SD) of the responses of the participants on the principals' administrative role that can impact on teachers' productivity. The analysis indicated that over 80% of the respondents rated the items in a strongly agreed decision. The cluster mean (\bar{x}) 3.50 and is accepted as very strongly agreed. The cluster standard deviation 0.479, which indicates that there is not much deviation from the mean

4.1.2 - Research questions 2: What is the influence of principals' communication rule on teachers' productivity?

Table 2 - Frequencies, Means and Standard Deviation of the responses of the respondents on the impact of principals' communication rule on teachers' productivity N= 145

S/N	Items	Frequency of the response Scores					\bar{x}	SD	Decision
		0	1	2	3	4			
7	A well-planned communication channel helps the principal to collaborate effectively with teachers for academic support	-	-	-	82	63	3.43	.497	S. Agree
8	Proper communication enhances teachers' productivity as the teacher are properly informed about the missions and visions of the principal/ school	-	-	-	110	35	3.24	.429	S. Agree
9	Principals' holding of statutory and special meetings promotes good inter personal relationship and this enhances teachers' productivity	-	-	5	79	61	3.39	.555	S. Agree
10	Promotion of school community relationship by the principal motivates the teachers to be more effective	-	-	4	85	56	3.36	.536	S. Agree
Cluster							=3.36	0.536	

\bar{x} = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation, SA = Strongly Agree, A = Agree, SD = Strongly Disagree

Table 2 above shows the responses of the research question 2 which says the impact of principals' communication roles on teachers' productivity based on responses from 145 participants.

The data indicated the mean rating (\bar{x}) and the standard deviation (SD) of the responses of the participants the cluster mean (\bar{x}) 3.36 and is accepted as very strongly agreed. The cluster standard deviation 0.536, which indicates that there is not much deviation from the mean.

4.1.3 - Research questions 3: To what extent does the principals' sustainability of instructional materials influence teachers' productivity?

Table 3 - Frequencies, Means and Standard Deviation of the responses of the respondents on the extent the principals' sustainability of instructional materials influence teachers' productivity

S/N	Items	Frequency of the response Scores					\bar{x}	SD	Decision
		0	1	2	3	4			
11	To what extent does the principals' sustenance of instructional materials improves teachers instructional	-	-	3	95	47	3.30	.504	S. Agree
12	To what extent does the principals' maintenance of instructional materials impacts on teachers productivity	-	-	3	89	53	3.34	.519	S. Agree
13	To what extent does the principals' adequate supervision of instructional materials improves teachers effectiveness at work	-	-	3	89	53	3.34	.519	S. Agree
Cluster							=3.34	0.519	

\bar{x} = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation, SA = Strongly Agree, A = Agree, SD = Strongly Disagree

The data presented in table 3 above, the mean rating (\bar{x}) and the standard deviation (SD) of the responses of the participants on the extent to which principals' sustainability of instructional materials influence teachers' productivity

The analysis indicated that over 97% of the respondents rated the items in a strongly agreed decision.

The cluster mean (\bar{x}) 3.34 and is accepted as very strongly agreed. The cluster standard deviation 0.515, which indicates that there is not much deviation from the mean

4.1.4 - Research questions 4: What is the influence of principals' promotion of good work environment on teachers' productivity?

Table 4 - Frequencies, Means and Standard Deviation of the responses of the respondents on the impact of principals' promotion of good work environment on teachers' productivity?

S/N	Items	Frequency of the response Scores					\bar{x}	SD	Decision
		0	1	2	3	4			
14	Work environment promotes teachers' commitment to quality work production	-	-	2	71	72	3.48	.528	S. Agree
15	When the working environment is favorable it influences my teaching and the students learn better	-	-	-	62	83	3.57	.496	S. Agree
16	Early payment of staff salary motivates teachers to do work better	-	-	1	39	105	3.72	.467	S. Agree
17	Good pay influences teachers' commitment to their work	-	-	-	51	51	94	3.65	S. Agree
18	When a principal promotes discipline in school, it leads to positive attitude to work by teachers	-	-	6	116	23	3.12	.433	S. Agree
Cluster							3.50	0.479	

\bar{x} = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation, SA = Strongly Agree, A = Agree, SD = Strongly Disagree

The data presented in table 4 above, the mean rating (\bar{x}) and the standard deviation (SD) of the responses of the participants on the impact of principals' promotion of good work environment on teachers' productivity. The cluster mean (\bar{x}) 3.50 and is accepted as very strongly agreed. The cluster standard deviation 0.479, which indicates that there is not much deviation from the mean

4.1.5 - Research questions 5: What are the ways of improving teachers' productivity through principals' administrative roles?

Table 5 - Frequencies, Means and Standard Deviation of the responses of the respondents on the ways of improving teachers' productivity through principals' administrative rule

		N= 145					\bar{x}	SD	Decision
S/N	Items	Frequency of the response Scores							
		0	1	2	3	4			
19	Principals involvement of teachers in decision-making can improve their productivity	-	-	21	105	19	2.99	.527	Agree
20	Principal's regular inspection of what the teachers do in class can make the teachers committed to their teaching and enhance their productivity	-	-	1	98	46	3.31	.479	S. Agree
21	Class supervision by the principal improves the quality of teacher work	-	-	-	64	81	3.56	.498	
22	Principal's ensuring of discipline in my school-promotes teachers confidence to work	-	-	8	123	14	3.04	.389	Agree
23	Principal good interpersonal relationship with-the teacher can enhance teacher productivity	-	-	-	68	77	3.53	.501	S. Agree
24	Principal interest in teachers welfare motivate-the staff for greater productivity	-	-	-	24	121	3.83	.373	S. Agree
Cluster							3.38	0.465	

\bar{x} = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation, SA = Strongly Agree, A = Agree, SD = Strongly Disagree

In table 5 above, the findings indicated that various aspects of principals' administrative practices—such as involvement in decision-making, regular inspections, supervision, and fostering good relationships—are perceived positively by teachers as mechanisms to improve productivity.

The mean rating (\bar{x}) and the standard deviation (SD) of the responses of the participants on the impact of principals' ways of improving teachers' productivity through principals' administrative roles

. The cluster mean (\bar{x}) 3.38 and is accepted as very strongly agreed. The cluster standard deviation 0.465, which indicates that there is not much deviation from the mean

4.2 Test of Hypothesis

4.2.1 Hypothesis 1 – (H01) - There is no significant difference in the responses of secondary teachers in private and public schools regarding the impact of principals’ communication skills on their productivity.

Table 6 - Group’s Means, Standard Deviation and t-test on Hypothesis

S/N	Items	GP	\bar{x}	SD	t-Cal	P-Value	Decision
1	Principals' Communication roles can positivity enhance teachers productivity	85 60	3.61 3.80	.514 .403	.023	.981	NS
2	Provision of Instructional materials generates teacher productivity abilities	85 60	3.42 3.47	.497 .503	-.202	.840	NS
3	Principals' promotion of good work environment motivates the teachers to be committed and have positive attitude to work	85 60	3.27 3.18	.473 .390	1.174	.242	NS
4	Principals' maintaining of Staff and Students' Discipline promotes teachers' productivity	85 60	3.54 3.72	.524 .454	- 2.095	.038	S
5	Principals' maintenance of school facilities extend the lifespan and enhance proper utilization of the facilities	85 60	3.48 3.48	.503 .504	-.012	.991	NS
6	Principals accountability role activates teachers to yield better result	85 60	3.48 3.65	.503 .481	- 2.013	.046	S

GP= Group (Private=85, Public=60), \bar{x} = Mean, SD= Standard deviation, DF= 143, K= 0.05 level of significant.

Table 6 reveals that there is no significant difference in responses of the private and public school teachers respondent on most of the items, except items 4 and 6, which showed a significant difference. Also, it shows that the calculated P-values are higher than the 0.05 level of significance, except for items 4 and 6, with p-values of .038 and .046 respectively. Basically, this implies that the views of both the public and private school respondents on the impact of principal’s communication skills on teachers’ productivity did not differ Therefore the null hypothesis 1 is accepted

4.2.2 – Hypothesis 2 – (H02)- There is no significant difference in the responses of private and public teachers concerning the influence of principals’ sustainability of instructional materials on their productivity.

Table 7 - Group’s Means, Standard Deviation and t-test on Hypothesis

S/N	Items	GP	\bar{x}	SD	t-Cal	P-Value	Decision
7	A well-planned communication channel helps the principal to collaborate effectively with teachers for academic support	85 60	3.44 3.43	.499 .500	.023	.981	NS
8	Proper communication enhance teachers' productivity as the teacher are properly informed about the missions and visions of the principal/ school	85 60	3.24 3.25	.427 .437	-.202	.840	NS
9	Principals' holding of statutory and special meetings promotes good inter personal relationship and this enhances teachers' productivity	85 60	3.35 3.43	.592 .500	-.858	.392	NS
10	Promotion of school community relationship by the principal motivates the teachers to be more effective	85 60	3.32 3.42	.561 .497	- 1.097	.275	NS

GP= Group (Private=85, Public=60), \bar{x} = Mean, SD= Standard deviation, DF= 143, K= 0.05 level of significant.

Table 7 reveals that there is no significant difference in responses of the private and public schools teachers respondent on all the items. Also, it shows that the calculated P-value are higher than the 0.05 level of significance. Basically, this implies that the views of both the public and private school respondents on the extent of principals’ provision of instructional materials can influence teachers’ productivity did not differ Therefore the null hypothesis 2 is accepted

5. **4.2.3 – Hypothesis 3 (H₀₃):** There is no significant difference in teachers' response regarding the impact of principals' promotion of a favourable working environment on their productivity in private secondary schools versus public secondary schools.

Table 8 - Group's Means, Standard Deviation and t-test on Hypothesis

S/N	Items	GP	\bar{x}	SD	t-Cal	p-Value	Decision
11	To what extent does the principals' sustenance of instructional materials improves teachers instructional	85 60	3.40 3.17	.561 .376	2.8 08	.006	S
12	To what extent does the principals' maintenance of instructional materials impacts on teachers productivity	85 60	3.34 3.35	.547 .481	- .10 1	.920	NS
13	To what extent does the principals' adequate supervision of instructional materials improves teachers effectiveness at work	85 60	3.40 3.27	.561 .446	1.5 31	.128	NS

GP= Group (Private=85, Public=60), \bar{x} = Mean, SD= Standard deviation, DF= 143, K= 0.05 level of significant.

Table 8 reveals that there is no significant difference in responses of the private and public schools teachers respondent on most of the items, except item 11, which showed a significant difference. Also, it shows that the calculated P-value are higher than the 0.05 level of significance, except for item 11, with a p-value of .006. Basically, this implies that the views of both the public and private school respondents on the impact of principal promotion of good work environment on teachers' productivity.

did not differ Therefore the null hypothesis 3 is accepted

4.2.4 – Hypothesis 4 (Ho₄): There is no significant difference in teachers’ responses about methods for enhancing productivity through principals’ administrative roles between those in private secondary schools and those in public secondary schools.

Table 9 - Group’s Means, Standard Deviation and t-test on Hypothesis

S/N	Items	GP	\bar{X}	SD	t-Cal	p-Value	Decision
14	Work environment promotes teachers' commitment to quality work production	85	3.38	.534	-	.004	S
		60	3.63	.486	2.960		
15	When the working environment is favorable it influences my teaching and the students learn better	85	3.56	.499	-.222	.825	NS
		60	3.58	.497			
16	Early payment of staff salary motivates teachers to do work better	85	3.62	.511	-	.004	S
		60	3.85	.360	2.952		
17	Good pay influences teachers' commitment to their work	85	3.60	.493	-	.149	NS
		60	3.72	.454	1.449		
18	When a principal promotes discipline in school, it leads to positive attitude to work by teachers	85	3.15	.362	1.183	.239	NS
		60	3.07	.516			

GP= Group (Private=85, Public=60), \bar{X} = Mean, SD= Standard deviation, DF= 143, K= 0.05 level of significant

Table 9 reveals that there is no significant difference in responses of the private and public schools teachers’ on most of the items, except items 14 and 16, which showed a significant difference. Also, it shows that the calculated P-value are higher than the 0.05 level of significance, except for items 14 and 16, with a p-value of .004 each. Basically, this implies that the views of both the public and private school respondents on the way of improving teachers’ productivity through principal’s administrative roles did not differ Therefore the null hypothesis 4 is accepted

4.3 - Summary of the Findings

Using a sample of 145 teachers, the analysis of survey responses indicates a general consensus that effective principal leadership positively correlates with increased teacher productivity. The findings reveal that principals' communication roles, provision of instructional materials, and promotion of a conducive work environment are perceived as critical factors. Specifically, the study records high mean scores and low standard deviations across the board, suggesting strong agreement among respondents regarding these elements. For instance, the cluster mean for the

impact of communication roles was 3.36, while the provision of instructional materials garnered a mean of 3.34, both of which reflect significant levels of agreement.

Moreover, the study examines hypotheses related to potential differences in perceptions between teachers in public and private schools. The results show no statistically significant differences in responses, implying that both groups recognize the importance of these administrative facets equally.

In conclusion, the research underscores the pivotal role of principals in shaping teachers' work environments and productivity. It emphasizes the need for effective communication, adequate resources, and a supportive atmosphere to foster teacher engagement and performance. The consistent agreement in responses highlights an overarching belief in the influence of principled administrative practices on educational outcomes, suggesting avenues for school leadership development in Nasarawa State.

The following are the major findings

- Respondents agreed that principals' communication roles positively influence teachers' productivity, with a mean score of 3.69. Effective communication was seen as essential for aligning teachers with school objectives and improving morale.
- The teachers recognized the importance of principals providing instructional materials, generating a mean score of 3.44. The sustainability and maintenance of these resources were linked to enhanced instructional effectiveness, reflected in a mean score of 3.34.
- A favourable work environment was strongly linked to teachers' commitment and productivity, with mean scores of 3.57 for favourable conditions and 3.72 for early salary payments as motivators. This emphasizes the importance of financial incentives and a supportive atmosphere.

- Significant differences were found in teachers' perceptions of principals' maintenance of discipline and accountability roles (p-values of 0.038 and 0.046, respectively), indicating that these factors contribute significantly to productivity in different school contexts.
- Principals engaging teachers in decision-making processes was highlighted as a potential avenue for enhancing productivity, with a mean score just below the threshold for strong agreement (2.99). Thus, more involvement could further improve teacher effectiveness.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, DISCUSSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter presents Discussion of the findings, Conclusion, Implications of the study, Recommendations, Contribution to knowledge and Suggestions for further study.

5.1 Discussion of the Findings

This study examined the principals' administrative roles and how they influence teachers' productivity. The central aim was to evaluate how different aspects of principal leadership functions influence the effectiveness and productivity of teachers, thereby enhancing educational goals in secondary schools in Karu LGA, Nasarawa State.

The findings were presented through multiple research questions, each focusing on different dimensions of principal administrative roles. The responses were drawn from a sample of 145 participants, resulting in significant insights into the perceptions of teachers regarding their principals. The overall cluster mean for the administrative roles was calculated at 3.50, indicating a strong consensus among respondents on the positive impact of these practices on teacher productivity.

One of the most striking findings was the importance of principals' communication skills. Respondents indicated that effective communication is vital for fostering collaboration and academic support among staff, with a mean score of 3.43. This suggests that clear and well-planned communication channels facilitate better relationships between principals and teachers, thereby positively impacting the educational environment. Relatedly, clarity regarding the school's mission and vision also positively impacted teachers' productivity, as reflected in a mean score of 3.24.

Furthermore, the sustenance of instructional materials emerged as key factor influencing teacher performance. With mean scores of 3.30 and 3.34, respectively, the results demonstrate that

principals who prioritize the availability and functionality of instructional resources enable teachers to perform more effectively. This aligns with educational theories emphasizing the link between resource availability and teaching quality.

The promotion of a favorable work environment was another significant aspect highlighted by the findings. Mean scores of 3.48 and 3.57 suggest that elements such as supportive working conditions, early payment of salaries, and overall financial remuneration play crucial roles in motivating teachers. A conducive work environment fosters commitment to quality work and enhances student learning outcomes. Moreover, despite the lower score of 3.12 related to discipline promotion, there was still general agreement that maintaining discipline in schools positively influences teachers' attitudes and commitment to their roles.

The study also explored the extent to which principals' administrative roles can enhance teachers' productivity through various mechanisms. For instance, although involvement in decision-making received a mean score of 2.99, suggesting a less robust agreement, regular inspections (mean score of 3.31) and class supervision (mean score of 3.56) were identified as significantly positive practices that enhance teacher commitment and effectiveness. Respondents perceived that principals' active roles in these areas directly correlate to improved productivity.

Moreover, hypothesis testing revealed interesting differences in perceptions between public and private school teachers. For instance, significant differences were found in how both groups viewed the roles of principals in maintaining discipline and accountability. The findings from the study underscore the multifaceted role that principals play in influencing teachers' productivity.

Effective communication, sustenance of instructional materials, and the cultivation of a supportive work environment are pivotal in fostering an atmosphere conducive to teaching and learning. The differences observed between public and private schools indicate that principals may need to tailor their administrative approaches to maximize teacher effectiveness in diverse educational contexts.

Ultimately, the study illustrates the critical position of school principals in shaping educational outcomes in Karu L.G.A, thus serving as a vital component in the broader discourse on educational leadership and teacher performance.

The overall results agree with the existing literature on educational leadership and strongly support the hypothesis that effective principal administration impacts teacher productivity positively. The following are the specific findings, comparison with previous research, and personal interpretation of the study:

Finding on principal's Communication roles: The study found strong consensus among respondents regarding the importance of principals' communication roles, which received a mean score of 3.43. This suggests that effective communication channels between principals and teachers facilitate collaboration and academic support. **In comparison** with Previous Research, existing literature, including a study by Ndal, Osuji & Wey – Amaehule (2022), emphasizes the need for efficient communication between school leaders and the success of their administrative efforts. They argue that Communication lays the groundwork for effective action and clears the way for a more cooperative workplace.

Personal Interpretation: The findings of this study corroborate the existing research, validating the belief that transparency and clarity in communication are key components of a successful educational environment. Effective communication can lead to improved relationships, higher productivity, and ultimately better student outcomes. This alignment suggests that school administrators who actively maintain open lines of communication will likely see an uptick in teacher commitment and efficacy, justifying the investment in communication strategies within educational institutions.

Finding on principal sustainability of instructional Materials: The study also highlighted the significant impact of principal's sustainability of instructional materials, with mean scores of 3.30

and 3.34, respectively. Respondents perceived that when principals ensure the availability and upkeep of instructional resources, teachers are more likely to perform effectively. **In comparison** with previous research, literature from Olumorin, Yusuf, Ajidagba and Jekayinfa (2010) observed that instructional materials help teachers to teach conveniently and the learners to learn easily without any problem. They asserted that instructional materials have direct contact with all sense organs.

Personal Interpretation: The results of this study echo these earlier findings, suggesting that administrators must prioritize resource provision as a fundamental aspect of their responsibilities. The alignment of these findings underscores the necessity of instructional materials in shaping teacher productivity, further justifying the role of school principals in advocating for and securing these resources.

Finding on principal's roles in promotion of a good work environment: Another critical finding was that principals' efforts to promote a positive work environment significantly affects teacher productivity, as reflected in the mean scores of 3.48 for commitment to work and 3.57 for favorable working conditions. **In Comparison** with previous research, this finding agrees with studies by Al-Omari and Okasheh (2017) that improving the working environment will motivate the employees for enhance performance in achieving the desires outcomes and goals of the organisation there by increasing employers' satisfaction. Usop, Askandar, Kadlong and Usop (2013) concluded in their study that the more teachers are satisfied with their jobs, the more productive they would be at work. These authors further noted that satisfied teachers would normally develop and maintain high levels of performance.

Personal Interpretation: The results affirm the established link between a positive work environment and teacher productivity. This study highlights that while financial incentives are important, non-monetary factors such as emotional well-being and supportive workplace culture are

equally crucial. Thus, principals should consider both aspects when aiming to enhance teacher effectiveness.

- **Finding on Maintenance of Discipline:** The study established that effective maintenance of discipline is perceived as vital for promoting teachers' productivity, receiving a higher mean score of 3.61. Respondents indicated that principals' efforts in this area led to better commitment and positive attitudes among teachers. **In comparison** with previous research, by Ñzokurum & Iremeka (2017), the principals should declare zero tolerance on any disruptive behaviour in and outside the classrooms in secondary school in order to present teachers with well cultured students for enhanced productivity.

Personal Interpretation: The importance of discipline as highlighted by this study emphasizes how foundational a structured environment is for both students and teachers. The findings fall in line with previous research, suggesting that when educators perceive that principals are effectively managing discipline, they feel more secure and supported in their roles. Consequently, it becomes imperative for school leaders not only to promote discipline but also to employ strategies that ensure its enforcement consistently.

Finding on the Impact of Salary Payments: This study found that elements such as timely salary payments significantly impact teacher satisfaction and productivity, with a mean score of 3.72.

This underscores the role of financial compensation as a motivator for teachers. **In comparison** with previous research, previous studies, including that of Ogunyemi, Adewole and Akinde (2019), the study concluded that remuneration package such as overtime, constant remuneration promotes morale and increase team cohesion. There was a significant relationship between effect of remuneration package and employee performance.

Personal Interpretation: The findings of this study validate the notion that while non-monetary motivators are essential, financial remuneration remains a pivotal factor in enhancing teacher

productivity. This suggests that principals must not only be aware of the importance of fair compensation but actively advocate for prompt salary disbursement to sustain a motivated teaching staff. The reinforcement of this factor is vital in promoting a positive working environment that fosters teacher retention.

In conclusion, the findings of this study reveal a comprehensive understanding of how principals' administrative roles directly impact teachers' productivity in Karu L.G.A, Nasarawa State. The significance of communication, resource provision/sustenance, work environment, discipline, and financial incentives all emerged as pivotal in enhancing teacher effectiveness. Additionally, the variations in perception between public and private school teachers underscore the importance of context in educational leadership. These results are consistent with previous research, validating the critical role of principals in fostering a conducive environment for teaching and learning.

By confirming the linkages identified in prior studies and providing additional context-specific insights, this study advances the discourse on educational leadership. Ultimately, these findings highlight the essential nature of effective school management and the need for future research to continue exploring the dynamic relationships in educational leadership and teacher productivity.

5.2 Implications of the Study

The study reveals significant insights into the administrative roles of principals and their influence on teachers' productivity in Karu L.G.A., Nasarawa State. The findings show the necessity of effective communication, provision and maintenance of instructional materials, fostering a conducive work environment, and active involvement in decision-making. The overall consensus among teachers suggests that principals' administrative practices positively influence productivity, emphasizing the need for leadership that prioritizes collaboration and support. Notably, differences between public and private school teachers regarding discipline maintenance and accountability point to the necessity for tailored administrative strategies. The implications of this research

highlight how principals can enhance teacher efficacy and satisfaction by developing effective communication channels and involving teachers in decision-making processes. These insights contribute to the broader understanding of educational management and suggest further exploration of context-specific leadership practices to foster productive teaching environments across diverse educational settings.

5.4 Conclusion

The findings underscore the critical role of effective communication, provision of teaching materials and promotion of good work environment in educational leadership and their influence on teachers' productivity. Future research could further explore these dynamics to provide deeper insights into effective leadership practices across different educational contexts in Nigeria. The study suggests that while there are areas of consensus regarding communication's importance, targeted improvements in specific areas such as discipline maintenance and accountability could yield significant benefits for both public and private school environments.

5.4 Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following are recommended:

1. It is recommended that principals establish well-structured communication channels to facilitate collaboration between teachers and administration. Regular meetings and feedback sessions should be institutionalized to ensure clarity of objectives and to promote a supportive environment.
2. Principals should prioritize the provision of necessary resources and develop strategies for continuous evaluation and sustainability of these materials to bolster teaching effectiveness. Regular training sessions on effective use and maintenance of these resources can be beneficial.

3. Principals should focus on creating a conducive work atmosphere, which includes ensuring timely salary payments and addressing teacher welfare comprehensively, as financial incentives were shown to significantly motivate teachers.

5.5 Contribution to Knowledge

1. The study provides empirical evidence on the significant role of principals' administrative functions in enhancing teacher productivity in Karu Local Government Area, Nasarawa State, Nigeria.
2. It identifies essential administrative roles—effective communication, provision of instructional materials, creation of a positive work environment, and promotion of discipline as instrument that influence teachers' productivity.
3. By establishing a clear link between administrative practices and teacher productivity, the research offers actionable recommendations for educational leadership aimed at optimizing performance.
4. The findings empower school leaders to adopt evidence-based practices, promote participatory decision-making, and create conducive environments for teaching and learning.
5. The study addresses existing gaps regarding administrative influences on teacher productivity and serves as a valuable resource for future research and policy formulation.
6. It highlights differences in perceptions of administrative roles between public and private school teachers, offering insights into the contextual factors shaping educators' experiences and attitudes.
7. The findings emphasize the need for good leadership strategies to enhance teacher productivity in varying school types, clarifying how principals can effectively improve educational outcomes.

5.6 Suggestions for Further Study

The findings of this study suggest several areas for future research which include:

1. More research could be conducted to examine the long-term impacts of principals' administrative roles on teachers' productivity, allowing for changes over time to be observed.
2. Further study is needed also to examine whether the findings of this study are applicable to secondary schools in other states in Nigeria
3. A study that explores differences in principals' effectiveness in both urban and rural settings within Nasarawa State to assess contextual impacts on teacher productivity can be carried out
4. Work that employs qualitative methods (interviews, focus groups) to gain deeper insights into teachers' perceptions and experiences regarding administrative practices not fully captured by quantitative measures.
5. Investigate the impact of external factors (e.g., socio-economic conditions, community involvement) on the relationship between principals' admin roles and teacher productivity.
6. Lastly study should be carried out to assess the effectiveness of training programs for principals aimed at enhancing their leadership skills, particularly in communication and resource management, to determine their influence on teacher performance.

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Appendices 1 – Letter of Introduction

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WUSE II/WISE II/INTRO/046/VOL. I

7th September, 2024

Chief Executive Officer,
School Manager,
Karama, Adamawa State

Rev. E. O. Okeke
SCHOOL
C/O

LETTER OF INTRODUCTION – ODION HENRY JUSTINA

I want to introduce **ODION HENRY JUSTINA – NDU232164897** an M.Ed Administration and Planning student in the Department of Education Foundation, Faculty of Education, WUSE II Study Centre, National Open University of Nigeria.

The student is currently carrying out a research on "Impact of Principals' Administrative roles on Teachers' Productivity in Rural Local Government" from the University.

In view of the above, the student while conducting her research will be collecting relevant data from the school/office.

Please accord her all necessary support required.

Thank you

Prof. Samuel B. Okeke
Director, WUSE II Study Centre

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NOUN/WUSE II/INTRO/045/VOL. I

7th September, 2024

The Principal,
Ambassador Sky Pathway Academy
New Nyanya,
Karu L.G.A Nasarawa State.

PRINCIPAL
AMBASSADOR SKY
ACADEMY
SIGN: *[Handwritten Signature]*

LETTER OF INTRODUCTION - ODION HENRY JUSTINA

I write to introduce **ODION HENRY JUSTINA - NOU232154897** an M.Ed Administration and Planning student in the Department of Education Foundation, Faculty of Education, WUSE II Study Centre, National Open University of Nigeria.

The student is currently carrying out a research on **"Impact of Principals' Administrative roles on Teachers' Productivity in Karu Local Government"** from the University.

In view of the above, the student while conducting her research will be collecting relevant data from the school/office.

Please accord her all necessary support required.

Thank you.

[Handwritten Signature]
Prof. Samson E. Osoba
Director, WUSE II Study Centre

Appendices 2 – Letter of attestation

PRINCIPAL
AMBASSADOR SKY
11/sep/2024

Department of Education Foundations,
Faculty of Education,
National Open University of Nigeria,
Jabi Abuja.
9th September, 2024.

The Principal,

Ambassador Sky Pathway Academy
Plot NO-288, Karu Phase II,
Newt Nyanya, Karu LGA, Nasarawa State

Letter of attestation and affirmation

This is to affirm that Odion Justina Henry with Matric number NOU232154897 collected data from the above mentioned organization for her research work on the topic **Principals' Administrative Role on Teachers' Productivity in Karu Local government area of Nasarawa State**

Sign

Affirmation

Date

11th Sept., 2024

Department of Education Foundations,
Faculty of Education,
National Open University of Nigeria,
Jabi Abuja.
9th September, 2024.

The Principal,

Divine Fortune int'l Academy,
Angwan Doka,
Karu LGA, Nasarawa State

Letter of attestation and affirmation

This is to affirm that Odion Justina Henry with Matric number NOU232154897 collected data from the above mentioned organization for her research work on the topic **Principals' Administrative Role on Teachers' Productivity in Karu Local government area of Nasarawa State**

Sign

Odion Justina Henry

Date

13th / 9 / 2024

7	A proper and a well-planned communication channel helps the principal to collaborate effectively with teachers for academic support (Please turn over)				
8	Proper communication enhances teachers' productivity as the teachers are properly informed about the missions and visions of the principal/school				
9	Principals' holding of statutory and special meetings promotes good inter personal relationship and this enhances teachers' productivity				
10	Promotion of school-community relationship by the principal motivates the teachers to be more effective.				
	R.Q. 3: To what extent does the principals' sustainability of instructional materials influence teachers' productivity?	VHE	HE	LE	VLE
11	To what extent does the principals' sustenance of instructional materials improves teachers' instructional delivery?				
12	To what extent does the principals' maintenance of instructional materials impacts on teachers' productivity?				
13	To what extent does the principal's adequate supervision of instructional materials improves teachers' effectiveness at work?				
	R.Q. 4: What is the influence of principals' promotion of good work environment on teachers' productivity?	SA	A	D	SD
14	Work environment promotes teachers' commitment to quality work production.				
15	When the working environment is favourable, it influences my teaching and the students learn better				
16	Early payment of staff salary motivates teachers to do work Better				
17	Good pay influences teachers' commitment to their work				
18	When a principal promotes discipline in school, it leads to positive attitude to work by teachers.				
	R. Q 5: What are the ways of improving teachers' productivity through principals' administrative roles?	SA	A	D	SD
19	Principals involvement of teachers in decision making can improve their productivity				
20	Principal's regular inspection of what the teachers do in class can make the teachers committed to their teaching and enhance their productivity.				
21	Class supervision by the principal improves the quality of teachers' work				
22	Principal's ensuring of discipline in my school promotes teachers confidence to work				
23	Principals' good interpersonal relationship with the teachers can enhance teachers productivity				
24	Principal interest in teachers welfare motivates the staff for greater productivity				

Request for Validation of Instrument

Department of Educational foundations,
Faculty of Education
National Open University of Nigeria.
VALIDATION OF INSTRUMENT

**Topic: Influence of Principals' Administrative Roles on Teachers' Productivity
in Karu L. G. A. of Nasarawa State.**

by

Odion Justina Henry
(NOU232154897)

M.Ed. Educational Administration and Planning

Purpose of the Study

The primary aim of this study is to explore the influence of principals' administrative roles on teachers' productivity within secondary schools in the Karu Local Government Area of Nasarawa State. Specifically, this research seeks to achieve the following objectives:

6. Identify and analyze the key administrative roles of principals that significantly affect teachers' productivity in the region.
7. Investigate the specific impact of principals' communication strategies on enhancing teachers' effectiveness.
8. Assess how the sustainability of instructional materials managed by principals influences teachers' productivity levels.
9. Evaluate the role of principals in fostering a conducive working environment and its effect on teachers' commitment and output.
10. Propose actionable recommendations to enhance teachers' productivity through effective administrative practices by principals

1.5 Research Questions

1. What are the principals' administrative roles that can influence teachers' productivity in Karu L.G.A. of Nasarawa State?
2. What is the influence of principals' communication roles on teachers' productivity?
3. To what extent does the principals' sustainability of instructional materials influence teachers' productivity?
4. What is the influence of principals' promotion of a good working environment on teachers' productivity?
5. What are the ways to improve teachers' productivity through principals' administrative roles?

Research Hypotheses

6. H01 - There is no significant difference in the responses of secondary teachers in private and public schools regarding the impact of principals' communication skills on their productivity.
7. H02- There is no significant difference in the responses of private and public teachers concerning the influence of principals' sustainability of instructional materials on their productivity.
8. H03 - There is no significant difference in teachers' response regarding the impact of principals' promotion of a favourable working environment on their productivity in private secondary schools versus public secondary schools.
9. H04 - There is no significant difference in teachers' responses about methods for enhancing productivity through principals' administrative roles between those in private secondary schools and those in public secondary schools.

Sir/Ma,

I will appreciate if you can help validate my instrument to ensure that it addresses my research questions. Thank you.

Odion Justina Henry

Appendices 5 - Acknowledgement from Ministry of Education, Karu LGA

The director/CHB,
Ministry of Education,
Karu zonal/Area office,
Karu Local Govt.

[Signature]
Chief Evaluation Officer
AECEO
Karu, Nasarawa State
Date: *[Signature]*

Acknowledged

Dear Sir,

The researcher is an M.Ed. student of National Open University of Nigeria carrying out a study on the topic "**Principals' Administrative Role on Teachers' Productivity in Karu Local government area of Nasarawa State**". I will appreciate if you can help provide the following data concerning public and private schools in Karu Local government:

- Number of public secondary schools in the Karu LGA 24
- Number of teachers in public secondary schools in the local govt. _____
- Num of registered/government approved private schools in Karu LGA 600

Yours' Faithfully,
Odion Justina Henry
(The researcher)
0803 873 7187

Appendices 6 – Project topic proposal

NATIONAL OPEN UNIVERSITY OF NIGERIA

NAME: ODION HENRY JUSTINA
MATRIC NO: NOU232154897
FACULTY: EDUCATION
PROGRAMME: M.ED ADMINISTRATION AND PLANNING
LEVEL: 800
COURSE CODE/TITLE: EDU820/DISSERATION PROJECT
EMAIL ADDRESS: nou232154897@noum.edu.ng
PHONE NUMBER: 08038737187
STUDY CENTRE: WUSE II

PROPOSED PROJECT TOPICS

1. IMPACT OF EFFECTIVE ADMINISTRATION OF SECONDARY SCHOOL ON STUDENT ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE.
2. PRINCIPALS LEADERSHIP STYLE AND ADMINISTRATIVE EFFECTIVENESS IN SECONDARY SCHOOL.

✓ 3. IMPACT OF PRINCIPAL ADMINISTRATIVE SKILLS AND ^{ON} TEACHERS PRODUCTIVITY.
ROLE/DUTIES

Approved
19/4/24
Dr. M. C. Mbanefo

Appendices 7 - Project topic approval

FACULTY OF EDUCATION

RESEARCH TOPIC APPROVAL FORM

Name of Student: Odion Justina Henry
Student's Matric No: NOU232154897
Programme of Study: M. Ed Administration and Planning
Study Centre: Wuse II
Research Topic: IMPACT OF PRINCIPALS' ADMINISTRATIVE ROLES/DUTIES ON TEACHERS' PRODUCTIVITY.

Approval:

1. Supervisor's Remark: The topic has been restructured and its ok.
D. M. C. Mbanofo 19/11/2019
Name and Signature of Supervisor with Date

2. Centre Director's Remark: _____

Name and Signature of Director with Date

3. Dean's Remark: _____

Name and Signature of Dean, FoE with Date

Appendices 8 – List of all public secondary schools and some private schools in Karu

	List of all public secondary schools in Karu LGA	List of some private schools in Karu LGA
1	GSS Karu	Ambassador Sky Pathway Academy New Nyanya
2	GSS Mararaba Gurku	Abuja Int'l School Maraba
3	GSS Aso Pada	Achievers School New Nyanya
4	GSS Nyanya Gbagyi	Aunty Alice School Mararaba
5	GSS Masaka	Babcecil Comprehensive High School New Karu
6	GSS Karu East	Brightway Int'l School New Nyanya
7	GSS Kugbaru	Bill Clinton College New Nyanya
8	GSS Kabusu	Channels of Blessing Academy New Nyanya
9	GSS Gurku	Char-rah Prime Academy Kuchikau
10	GDSS Kodape	City Stars Academy Ado
11	GJSS Karu Central	Divine Int'l Children School New Nyanya
12	GJSS Maraba Gurku	Faith Academy Goshen
13	GJSS Aso Pada	Fountain of Knowledge Int'l school Uke
14	GJSS Nyanya Gbagyi	God's Love College Kuchikau
15	GJSS Masaka	God's Own School Masaka
16	GJSS Luvu Madaki	High Grace Int'l School Maraba
17	GJSS Jikwoyi	Innovative Schools New Karu
18	GJSS Nyanya Gwandara	K-Bols Int'l school Auta
19	GJSS Kugbaru	Legacy Int'l Academy
20	GJSS Gurku	Lyngra Private Montessori School, One Man Village
21	GJSS Ado Kugbo	Mount Carmel Int'l College New Nyanya
22	GJSS Koroduma	Peace And Privilege School Masaka
23	GSS Karshi	Potential Int'l school Masaka
24	GDSS Uke	Sister Sarah Eke Memorial School New Nyanya
25		St. Augustine College New Karu
26		St. Caleb Academy Koroduma
27		St. Philip Academy Mararaba Gurku
28		The Fountain School Masaka
29		Triton Int'l School Kuchikau
30		Pride of the Nation School New Nyanya
31		Royal College Masaka
32		Royal Model New Nyanya
33		Solid Fundamentals Montessori New Karu
34		The Lord's School Tudun Wada
35		Valliant Private School Ado
36		Vawa Int'l school New Nyanya
37		Victory Kiddies
38		Zanang Int'l school Auta
39		ECWA Faith Academy Panda
40		Fortress Int'l Academy Uke
41		Future Gate Model Academy Bakin Ado
42		Future Hope Academy Aku Village
43		Galaxy Academy Aso Pada
44		Goal Setters Academy Masaka
45		Good Treasure Int'l School New Karu